

FERROMAGNETIC ORDERING IN NANOSTRUCTURED CoPt AND SUPERCONDUCTIVITY IN NbN/CoPt HETEROSTRUCTURES

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CERTIFICATE

It is certified that the work contained in this thesis entitled “*Ferromagnetic ordering in nanostructured CoPt and superconductivity in NbN/CoPt heterostructures*”, by *Rajib Kumar Rakshit*, has been carried out under my supervision and that this work has not been submitted elsewhere for a degree.

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Studies of the correlation between crystallographic as well as morphological structure and magnetic coercivity of CoPt and FePt alloy films have been of considerable interest in recent years. Such research has been motivated primarily by the ever-increasing needs of the magnetic data recording industry for higher packing density combined with chemical stability of the storage medium which are met by CoPt and FePt alloys. A higher packing density naturally implies a much smaller magnetic entity. However, as the size of the grains becomes small enough to form single-

domains, the magnetic response of the granular sample differs significantly from that in the bulk. A controlled growth of nanoparticles and epitaxial films of these alloys and studies of magnetization and the process of its reversal in such structures is, therefore, an essential direction of research.

The perpendicular magnetic anisotropy in CoPt and FePt films also makes them promising for flux pinning in superconductors. Superconductor-ferromagnet (SC-FM) heterostructures, in general, show a rich variety of phenomena such as π -phase shift, triplet pairing, field enhanced superconductivity, domain wall superconductivity etc. An important issue that needs to be considered while addressing the physics of SC-FM-SC and FM-SC-FM heterostructures is the difference in the crystallographic structure and the degree of strain in the top and bottom SC or FM layers, and interdiffusion at interfaces which could impart different physical properties to the top and bottom layers. Thus far most of the studies in this area have been carried out on heterostructures of elemental superconductors such as Pb and Nb made in conjunction with 3d transition metal ferromagnets. It is expected that the competition between the SC and FM orders will have a different flavor if hard superconductors characterized by a short coherence length and large magnetic penetration depth are used. The nature of magnetic layers is not less important as field enhanced superconductivity and vortex pinning depend greatly on the domain structure and dynamics of domain wall motion in the magnetic layer.

The present study was primarily motivated by the desire to understand the effects of various deposition conditions on morphological, crystallographic and magnetic characteristics of equiatomic CoPt, and to investigate the relationship between high

coercivity and chemical ordering. Morphologically smooth CoPt films have also been investigated with superconducting NbN, and systematic experimental approach has been developed towards an understanding of some of the basic aspects of the interplay between superconductivity and magnetism in CoPt/NbN bilayer systems. The layout of the thesis is as follows:

Chapter 1 is an introduction to the basic concepts of magnetism and its evolution with chemical ordering in binary cobalt-platinum alloys. Crystallographic structure and the superconducting phase of NbN are discussed with a brief review on granularity aspects of superconducting NbN. The interplay of superconductivity and magnetism and its repercussion on superconductivity in hybrid structures have been reviewed. This chapter concludes with the identification of some critical issues of magnetism in CoPt and superconductivity in NbN/CoPt hybrids which are addressed in the subsequent chapters.

Chapter 2 presents a detailed layout of the various experimental procedures used in this thesis. In the first few sections we briefly explore the basic mechanism and advantages and drawbacks of the PLD technique. The concept of Pulsed Laser Ablation in Aqueous Medium (PLAAM) to fabricate colloidal solutions of metal and alloy nanoparticles is also introduced. In section 2.5 we have discussed Ar⁺ ion milling and maskless Focused Ion Beam (FIB) techniques for patterning of samples and to create 2-dimensional array of CoPt islands. Two-axis X-ray powder diffractometer for structural characterization is described thereafter. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), Transmission

Electron Microscopy (TEM), Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) and Magnetic Force Microscopy (MFM) have been introduced in the subsequent sections. We have used these techniques for investigation of topography and morphology of film surfaces and for imaging of magnetic domains. A Superconducting Quantum Interference Device (SQUID) based magnetometer, which was used for measurements of magnetization and magnetic relaxation, is introduced in section 2.8. The dynamics of vortices in NbN/CoPt heterostructures was investigated using a miniature Hall-probe based ac susceptometer. A brief discussion of this technique is presented in section 2.9. Finally, the standard four probe technique for measurements of resistivity, magnetoresistance and critical current density is briefed in section 2.10.

Chapter 3 presents synthesis of CoPt nanoparticles dispersed in surfactant polymer matrix using Pulsed Laser Ablation in Aqueous medium. The key advantage of this technique is in synthesis of multielemental nanoparticles of a desired stoichiometry without the use of hazardous chemicals. Studies of the magnetization dynamics of nanoparticles of the disordered low temperature fcc phase CoPt alloy are reported. The magnetization dynamics of these particles is examined in the framework of superparamagnetic blocking phenomenon based on log-normal size distribution. Our analysis reveals, in accordance with electron microscopy results, two size distributions which peak at 1.3 nm and 5.9 nm. The magnetic anisotropy energy of these particles is 0.9×10^6 J/m³ and 0.1×10^6 J/m³ respectively.

Chapter 4 deals with strained epitaxial CoPt films grown using PLD on single crystal substrates of different lattice parameter. The choice of different substrates allows tuning of the strain and hence the surface morphology of the films, which also depends on process parameters such as deposition temperature and growth rate, in addition to the degree of lattice match with the substrate. We note that the role of lattice mismatch in controlling the growth morphology of these films is important only when the flux of adatoms on the substrate is kept low. At high flux densities, kinetic effects suppress the morphological features which might have evolved due to an imbalance of strain and interfacial energies of the film. The best *c*-axis oriented epitaxial $L1_0$ CoPt thin films display a coercive field as high as ≈ 30 kOe and anisotropy energy density of $\sim 4.62 \times 10^6$ J/m³ at ambient temperature.

Chapter 5 discusses the effect of strain due to lattice mismatch and proximity-effect on superconductivity in CoPt/NbN bilayers. Two different bilayer systems with reversed deposition sequence are grown on MgO (001) substrates. It is observed that the epitaxial growth is greatly affected by the interfacial strain, particularly in the NbN-CoPt/MgO system where it makes the NbN film to adopt a strain-induced granular structure, which has interesting repercussions on superconductivity. Overall suppression of superconductivity as observed from magnetization and transport critical current measurements in this system compared to the other bilayer geometry suggests perturbation in the electronic structure although no direct evidence of suppressed superconducting order

parameter is observed from susceptibility measurements.

Chapter 6 discusses superconductivity in CoPt/NbN bilayers consisting of nanoengineered artificial structures. Here we argue that in FM-SC systems where the FM domains/islands produce spatial inhomogeneities of the SC order parameter, the observed FIS can derive significant contribution from different mobilities of the magnetic flux identified by two distinct critical states in the inhomogeneous superconductor. Our experiments on nanoengineered bilayers of ferromagnetic CoPt and superconducting NbN where CoPt/NbN islands are separated by a granular NbN, lend support to this alternative explanation of FIS in certain class of FM-SC hybrids.

Chapter 7 presents a brief summary of important results of our experiments on colloids and thin films of equiatomic CoPt alloy, and magnetic coupling and induced superconductivity in CoPt/NbN bilayers. Here we also identify some issues which are potentially interesting for further studies.

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LIST OF PUBLICATIONS

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction

The necessity for smaller and more efficient magnetic devices and the novel magnetic phenomena seen in low dimensional systems have fueled fundamental studies of nano-scale magnetism in a variety of materials and hybrid structures in recent years. Magnetic nanoparticles, for example, have attracted wide attention in the fields of high-density data storage, ferrofluids, hyperthermia treatment of cancers and drug-delivery systems. The physical properties of magnetic materials modify considerably as their size is reduced, particularly due to the increasing influence of surface spins. In addition, the exchange and anisotropy energies in these systems become comparable to thermal energy above a critical temperature giving rise to new size dependent effects. The best such example is superparamagnetism in small crystallites of ferromagnetic (antiferromagnetic) materials below Curie (Néel) temperature.

In this chapter we briefly review some basic aspects of magnetism with particular emphasis on the various types of magnetic ordering and some relevant energy scales like, magnetic exchange energy and magnetic anisotropy. Recent studies of the coexistence and competition between superconductivity (SC) and ferromagnetism (FM) in FM-SC hybrids have also been reviewed. Here we also give an introduction to ferromagnetism and superconductivity in materials which constitute the FM-SC heterostructures studied in this thesis. The chapter concludes with a statement of the motivation for undertaking the present work and an outline of the remaining

chapters of this thesis.

1.2 Bulk and nano-scale magnetism

1.2.1 Magnetic anisotropy

Preferential orientation of the bulk magnetization vector (\vec{M}) of a magnetic system inside the material, which leads to minimization of energy, is known as magnetic anisotropy. Several factors can induce such anisotropic distribution of the magnetic energy in a sample. Dominant among these factors is an intrinsic anisotropy related to the crystal structure of the system, referred as magnetocrystalline anisotropy. Magnetocrystalline anisotropy arises from the spin-orbit coupling effects in the system. Coupling of spin moments with the anisotropic orbital field of a lattice results a state where certain directions in the crystal are energetically more favorable for magnetization at zero applied magnetic field. Deviation of magnetic moments from these easy directions (axes) requires some energy known as anisotropy energy. Depending on the crystal structure and symmetry, there may be one or more easy magnetization axes in a material. In the simplest case of uniaxial anisotropy the magnetocrystalline anisotropy energy density is expressed as $K_u \cos^2\theta$, where K_u is the uniaxial anisotropy constant, and θ is the angle between the magnetization vector and the easy axis of magnetization. Magnetostriction is another manifestation of the magnetocrystalline anisotropy, where the anisotropy is induced due to crystal lattice deformation. In case of thin films, the surface contribution to anisotropy becomes comparable to the volume anisotropy energy and this often leads to in-plane orientation of the magnetic easy axes.

Another class of magnetic anisotropy, which becomes prominent at the nanoscale is the shape anisotropy. It appears due to the increasing effect of the demagnetizing field in magnetic samples of reduced dimensionality. The easy axis of magnetization

in a nanoscale magnetic specimen of random shape follows the direction of minimum demagnetizing field. For this reason, a spherical nanoparticle shows no shape anisotropy.

1.2.2 Magnetic domain structure in ferromagnets

An uniformly magnetized body minimizes its magnetostatic energy by subdivision of the areas of uniform magnetization into domains, each with a unique but randomly oriented direction of magnetization. Such magnetic domains are separated from each other by a transitional region of magnetization known as domain wall, where the direction of neighboring spins vary. The domain wall width is mainly determined by the competition between the exchange energy and the anisotropy energy. A lower anisotropy energy and higher exchange energy favor formation of thicker domain walls, whereas high magnetic anisotropy can reduce the domain wall width to as thin as 10 nm [1]. The domain structure and the nature of domain walls in a ferromagnetic material are intimately linked with the process of energy minimization. While the neighboring domains in bulk specimen are associated with the Bloch type domain wall in which the spin orientation within a wall changes by rotation about an axis perpendicular to the plane of the wall (see Fig. 1.1(a)), thin films have shown to exist with various types of domain walls other than Bloch wall, such as Néel, cross-tie, spiral and concentric circle, and double wall [2]. The presence of these types of domain walls in thin films depends on the local imperfections such as strain, easy-axis dispersion etc. and on the geometry of the sample. The simplest type of wall in a thin film is the Néel wall. As the thickness of the sample decreases, the magnetostatic energy of the wall increases as a result of the free poles at the top and bottom of the wall being separated by a distance equal to the film thickness. To minimize this magnetostatic energy the spins inside the wall need to rotate in the plane of the wall thus forming the Néel type wall (Fig. 1.1(b)). It has been shown

that the Bloch wall energy density decreases with increasing film thickness because of the increased magnetostatic energy. The Néel wall energy density on the other hand increases with increasing film thickness. Therefore, below a certain value of film thickness Néel wall is energetically more stable than the Bloch wall [2, 3].

Fig. 1.1: Spin rotation in domain walls: (a) Bloch type and (b) Néel type. The half-cycled arrow specifies the direction of spin rotation within domain wall (after Ref. [2]).

1.2.3 Magnetic nanoclusters

1.2.3.1 Single domain particles, superparamagnetism

Magnetic clusters below a critical size consist of a single magnetic domain, first predicted by Frenkel and Dorfman [4]. This state appears when the energy of domain wall formation becomes larger than the magnetostatic energy of the cluster. Diameters smaller than 30 nm for a spherical sample of the common ferromagnetic materials is essentially single domain as approximated by Kettel [5]. Moreover, if the cluster size is comparable to the exchange correlation length, which is governed by the square root of the ratio of the exchange stiffness and the energy cost of having spins oriented at a non-zero angle to the easy-axis, then all spins in the cluster are collinear, forming a so called super-spin [6, 7]. The magnetic order in bulk materials is driven by exchange interactions, which results in a ferromagnetic or an antiferro-

magnetic type of the magnetic order. The paramagnetic behavior is observed above the Curie temperature (for ferromagnet) and the Néel temperature (for antiferromagnet) when thermal fluctuations overcome the exchange interactions and lead to random fluctuations of atomic magnetic moments. A similar temperature dependent behavior is typical for magnetic nanoparticles. If we assume an uniaxial anisotropy of magnetic nanoparticles then the magnetic anisotropy energy due to the magnetocrystalline and shape anisotropy is given by $E(\theta) = K_u V \sin^2 \theta$, where θ is the angle between the magnetization direction and an easy direction of magnetization (easy axis), K_u is the uniaxial anisotropy constant, V is the volume of a nanoparticle. $K_u V$ is the anisotropy energy barrier at zero applied field separating both easy directions for the magnetization, which in zero magnetic field are along $\theta = 0$ and $\theta = \pi$. It is important to note that the height of the energy barrier depends on the particle size. As the volume of a cluster becomes smaller, above a certain temperature known as blocking temperature (T_b) thermal fluctuations become comparable to the magnetic anisotropy energy. Under such circumstances, the magnetization vector of the cluster fluctuates between its two easy axes ($\theta = 0$ and π). This results in a superparamagnetic relaxation, which, following the Néel-Brown expression is given as; $\tau = \tau_0 \exp(K_u V / k_B T)$ where τ_0 usually has a value of 10^{-9} sec [8]. An ensemble of such nanoclusters shows paramagnetic behavior above the blocking temperature. However, when the temperature drops below the T_b , the super-spin gets frozen in either up or down direction. This state is referred as the superparamagnetic phase.

Experimentally, T_b can be obtained from measurements of magnetization by zero-field cooled (ZFC) and field cooled (FC) procedures. While non-interacting ferromagnetic particles below T_b exhibits irreversible magnetization characterized by a peak in ZFC branch at $T = T_b$, both FC and ZFC measurements exhibits similar temperature dependence above T_b . The broadening of the peak, reported by several workers[9–12], is attributed to the particles size distribution. Furthermore,

magnetic behavior of a system of nanoparticles is commonly described in terms of a magnetically ordered core and a disordered surface layer. In small particles a major source of anisotropy results from surface effects due to a significant increase of the surface-to-volume ratio of atoms, compared to the bulk [13]. The reduction of the coordination number, i.e, the total number of the nearest neighbors around a single atom of surface atoms and the lack of translational symmetry at the particle surface can introduce frustration and spin disorder leading to a magnetic ground state which is different from the simple assumption of a single domain with a perfect magnetic ordering. The shell or ligand molecules which cover small particles in some cases also play an important role as they may alter electronic environment at the particle surface. Phenomenologically, the effective magnetic anisotropy for an assembly of nanoparticles can be described as $K_{eff} = K_v + SK_s/V$, where S and V are the surface area and volume of the particle respectively [14].

1.2.3.2 Magnetic cluster-assembled films

The important magnetic interactions that exist in fine particle assemblies are: (i) dipole-dipole interactions, (ii) exchange interactions and (iii), in granular solids, the RKKY interaction through a metallic matrix, or super exchange interaction when the matrix is insulating. The energy barrier due to anisotropy energy of each particle gets modified in the presence of magnetic interactions. In the limit of strong interactions, the contribution of individual particles become insignificant. The total energy of the assembly being the only relevant parameter. Such systems exhibit a complicated, spin-glass-like behavior [15]. Unlike the case of static energy barrier distribution arising only from the anisotropy contribution in non-interacting ensembles, here the reversal of one particle moment can alter the energy barriers of the assembly, resulting in a continuous modification of the energy barrier distribution as the magnetization relaxes. Consequently, the behavior of an assembly of interacting

magnetic nanoclusters in a field-temperature phase space (H-T) evolves in a different manner than the behavior of an assembly of non interacting nanocluster assembly. For instance, the isolated single domain magnetic particles while may have a high coercivity at temperatures below the superparamagnetic blocking temperature [16], the interacting magnetic nanogranular assemblies are magnetically soft due to the inter-cluster exchange phenomena. This issue has been discussed in ref. [17]. The inter-cluster exchange interaction initiates the process of coherent magnetization rotation [17]. Furthermore, numerical simulations for a system with random uniaxial anisotropy predicted that the coercive field (H_c) decreases linearly with the strength of dipolar interactions [18, 19]. An earlier study based on Monte Carlo (MC) simulation on the effect of dipolar interactions for a system of fine ferromagnetic particles predicted the possibility of both increase or decrease of H_c with volume packing factor depends on the geometrical arrangement of the particle moments and the direction of applied field [20].

In granular systems, dipolar and exchange interactions may exist simultaneously [15]. The results show that for a system of polydispersed grains having their anisotropy axes oriented at random, both remanence ratio and coercivity increase with increasing exchange interaction. On the contrary, when particles were located on a lattice, inter-granular exchange coupling has been predicted to increase the remanence ratio and reduce the H_c [21]. Besides these, for extremely high uniaxial anisotropic granular system such as FePt and CoPt, thermal stability of magnetization and the process of its reversal are greatly controlled by the grain boundaries. The reversal can occur either continuously through coherent or incoherent rotation of spins, or discontinuously, through nucleation of reversed domains and their local expansion through domain wall displacement [22, 23]. Growth of reverse domains can be impeded by defects, such as second-phase precipitates or physical grain boundaries in the case of granular thin films, which pin the domain walls by

locally altering the domain wall energy. The increase in coercivity is, therefore, intimately linked with the defect concentration and density of grain boundaries. In epitaxial films consisting of discontinuous islands/dots of sufficiently small size such that domain wall formation is energetically not favorable, the demagnetization process has several interesting features including quantum tunneling at sufficiently low temperatures [24].

1.3 The Cobalt-Platinum system

1.3.1 Structure and phase diagram

Fig. 1.2: The equilibrium phase diagram of bulk Co-Pt system (after Ref. [77]).

Amongst the alloys of the ferromagnetic 3d transition metals with paramagnetic 5d elements, the platinum based alloys have drawn much attention because of their fascinating magnetic and electronic properties. During the last few years, equiatomic cobalt-platinum (CoPt) alloy in various forms such as self-assembled nanoparticles, colloids and thin films has been a major topic of research in the area of magnetic

Fig. 1.3: Theoretically derived Co-Pt phase diagram (Adapted from Ref. [25]).

materials. The equilibrium phase diagram of bulk Co-Pt shown in Fig. 1.2 displays a continuous series of solid solutions with ferromagnetic order up to 90 at. % of Pt and the existence of two chemically ordered phases; CoPt and CoPt₃. However, there are three intermetallic ordered phases that exist at room temperature in thin film form. They are Co₃Pt, CoPt and CoPt₃. The ordered phases have cubic symmetry of L₁₂ (space group Pm3m) type near the 1:3 atomic ratio (Fig. 1.5(a)) and L₁₀ symmetry (Tetragonal) with space group P4/mmm near the 1:1 ratio (Fig. 1.4(b)). Although an L₁₂ cubic phase for Co₃Pt has been predicted theoretically by Sanchez et al. [25] (see Fig. 1.3), no experimental evidence has been found for its existence. However, an ordered hcp Co₃Pt has been prepared by several groups in thin film form (Fig. 1.5(b)) [26–29]. Each of these ordered phases exist over a wide range of compositions. For example, the L₁₀ structure is the equilibrium phase below 825

Fig. 1.4: Crystal structures of the (a) disordered and (b) ordered phases of the CoPt alloy.

$^{\circ}\text{C}$ between approximately 40 to 60 at. % of Pt. Outside the ordered phase regions CoPt has the disordered fcc structure [see Fig. 1.4(a)]. The $L1_0$ ordered phase has a slight tetragonality with $a = 3.803 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 3.701 \text{ \AA}$ giving a c/a ratio of 0.97 [30]. The ordered CoPt unit cell has alternating planes of Co and Pt in the $[001]$ direction and therefore this phase can be considered as a (1:1) multilayer structure of Co and Pt. Ordered CoPt phase is one of the hardest known permanent magnets.

1.3.2 Magnetism in cobalt-platinum

Elemental cobalt orders ferromagnetically at 1400 K. According to the Fig. 1.2, bulk Co_3Pt , CoPt and CoPt_3 show ferromagnetic transition with respective Curie temperature (T_c) of $\approx 1000 \text{ K}$, 710 K and 480 K. Self-consistent band structure calculations using localized spherical wave (LSW) method reveal saturation magnetization (M_s) for these phases to be 1000 emu/cc, 725 emu/cc and 400 emu/cc respectively [31]. In the case of films however, the T_c , M_s and H_c depend sensitively on growth conditions which affect the crystallinity and microstructure of the films. For example, a significant enhancement of T_c of about 200 K in thin films of CoPt_3 has been reported by Rooney et al. [32]. Strong growth induced uniaxial perpendic-

Fig. 1.5: Crystal structures of (a) $L1_2$ $CoPt_3$ and (b) ordered hcp phase of Co_3Pt .

ular magnetic anisotropy with an easy axis of magnetization perpendicular to the film plane has been observed by several authors [33–35]. The origin of perpendicular anisotropy observed in this system, however, remains unclear. Weller et al. [33] suggested that a growth related inhomogeneity may result in an equivalent interface anisotropy. Farrow et al. [33] proposed that the directional imbalance in Co-Co pairs at the interface between the ordered CoPt regions and the disordered Co-Pt regions induces perpendicular magnetic anisotropy in a partially ordered $CoPt_3$ system. On the other hand, by comparing the magnetic properties between the CoPt ($L1_0$) and $CoPt_3$ ($L1_2$) ordered phases in relation to the atomic arrangements in a unit cell, it is concluded by Park et al. [33] that the perpendicular magnetic anisotropy in this Co-Pt alloy system depends mainly on the atomic arrangements of the Co and Pt. Tyson et al. [36] suggested that the anisotropic distribution of Co-Co bonds (see Fig. 1.5(a)) is responsible for the observed high K_u . Magnetization measurements on $CoPt_3$ film with perpendicular anisotropy reported by Albrecht et al. [34] show a square hysteresis loop of almost 100 % remanence with saturation magnetization and coercive field of 520 emu/cc and 200 Oe respectively.

For Co-rich alloys where the composition ratio is close to 3:1, either a chemically

disordered or an ordered phase can be formed. Co_3Pt ordered structure consists of two kinds of layers; one with only Co atoms and the other consisting of equal number of Co and Pt atoms (see Fig. 1.5(b)). Bandhu et al. [27] have reported the transformation of lattice structure from a disordered, mixed fcc/hexagonal phase to a ordered and purely hexagonal phase with the increasing deposition temperature which returns to a disordered fcc phase at $T > 900$ K. These structural transitions are accompanied by large changes in magnetic anisotropy. For instance, magnetocrystalline anisotropy increases with the increasing volume fraction of the ordered phase and attains the maximum value of about 2×10^7 erg/cc [37]. The origin of the large perpendicular magnetic anisotropy in alloy thin films has been investigated by several workers [27, 37].

While the disordered CoPt with equiatomic composition is a soft ferromagnet, the ordered L1_0 phase is highly coercive, with coercivities in some cases well over 50 kOe. Indeed, it is this fact that has generated so much interest in CoPt and FePt alloys for permanent magnets and recording media applications. The L1_0 phase has a large (5×10^7 erg/cc) uniaxial magnetocrystalline anisotropy along the c -axis. The relationship between high coercivity and chemical ordering has received a great deal of attention. One school of thought believes that the highest value of H_c is associated with a state where both the disordered and ordered phases are present with equal abundance. The mechanism for the high coercivity as proposed by Newkirk et al. [38], takes into account the short range coherency strains between the ordered and disordered phase regions. The other school of thought associates the maximum coercivity with the fully ordered state [39, 40]. In most of these papers, the mechanism for high coercivity is the internal stress caused by the tetragonal ordering, especially at anti-phase boundaries, which resist domain wall motion or suppress the growth of domains of reverse magnetization.

1.4 Ferromagnet-Superconductor Hybrid (FSH) system

Superconductivity and ferromagnetism are two antagonistic quantum phenomena. Studies of the repercussion of this mutual dislike have been of great interest since the early work of Ginzburg, Abrikosov, de Gennes and other on superconductors with magnetic impurities [41]. Great advances in material processing techniques in recent years have allowed creation of novel ferromagnet-superconductor hybrids (FSH). Several effects of fundamental and technological importance, such as π -phase superconductivity, triplet pairing, flux pinning, domain wall superconductivity and field-enhanced superconductivity have been seen in such systems. In the following we provide a brief review of the work related to flux pinning and field-enhanced superconductivity in FSH systems.

1.4.1 Vortex pinning by magnetic dots

First experimental works on FSH were focused on flux pinning properties of magnetic dot arrays deposited on a thin superconducting film [42–46]. All real samples contain dislocations, stacking faults, point and surface defects to some extent. Such defects where the superconducting order parameter is either zero or greatly suppressed are preferential sites for localizing vortices because this amounts to save the condensation energy which would otherwise be lost in the vortex core. In this sense defects act as pinning centers and the cumulative effect of all the defects provides the bulk pinning force. Technological applications of superconductors depend crucially on their critical current density (J_c) which depends on the effective pinning strength and the distribution of pinning centers in the superconductor. One of the widely used methods to enhance the flux pinning in superconductors is to engineer microscopic defects that suppress superconductivity locally. Several new approaches have been introduced in recent years specifically for thin films. These methods include microscopic perforation of the films and patterning magnetic dots on the surface of

superconducting films. These techniques are based upon the fact that the locally suppressed superconducting regions pin the normal core of the vortices. However, another more effective way to realize high J_c is to pin the magnetic flux of the vortex rather than the core. It has been demonstrated that the pinning of the vortices by magnetic inhomogeneities in SC/FM multilayers can be two orders of magnitudes more effective than the pinning by columnar defects [47].

First experiments on flux pinning were performed with two-dimensional arrays of magnetic dots of several microns width and their magnetization parallel to the plane of the superconducting film [42, 43]. Flux pinning by a triangular array of submicron size dots magnetized in-plane was reported by Martin et al. [45]. They observed periodic oscillations in the magnetoresistance of the superconducting Nb film in the flux flow regime. These oscillations were attributed to a simple matching effect: pinning becomes stronger when vortex lattice is commensurate with the lattice of pinning centers. The dependence of vortex pinning by magnetic dots array on magnetic field direction was studied by Morgan and Ketterson [46]. They found a large difference in J_c when the magnetization of the dots was parallel and when antiparallel to the external field. This experiment emphasized the fact that the physics of vortex pinning by magnetic dots is different from that of the non-magnetic pinning centers.

The use of magnetic imaging techniques, namely scanning hall probe microscope (SHPM) and magnetic force microscope (MFM), in combination with transport measurements in recent years have provided new insight of vortex physics. For example, Van Bael et al. [48] have studied with SHPM the magnetization and vortex distribution in a thin Pb film covered with a square array of single domain cobalt dots with in-plane magnetization. These studies reveal a preferential pinning of flux lines on one side of the dots, which can be understood by considering the flux distribution in the superconductor due to the dipolar field of the dots and that

due to the external field.

In a recent study Van Bael et al. [49] have investigated with the SHPM the nature of vortex pinning in a Pb film by an array of Co/Pt dots with out-of-plane magnetization. Their field cooled SHPM images show that while in the case of the field parallel to the magnetization of the dots vortices reside on the dots, in antiparallel field vortices prefer to stay at interstitial positions in the magnetic-dot-lattice. The origin of this polarity dependent pinning has been explained in terms of several mutually dependent energy terms associated with the system. For the parallel configuration; (i) the screening current of a dot and supercurrent encircling a flux line partially cancel one another if the vortex is positioned on the dot, (ii) also, the magnetostatic energy reduction of the stray field outside the superconductor is much higher for the on site pinning. The cooperative effect of these two energy terms favors the vortex to be strongly pinned at the dots when both magnetization and external field line up parallel. For the antiparallel alignment, screening current and supercurrent both circulate in the same sense. Furthermore, magnetostatic energy of the stray field for on site vortex pinning is always larger than that for interstitial pinning. Therefore, for the case of antiparallel field the vortices are affixed interstitially leading to much weaker pinning strength.

1.4.2 Enhanced superconductivity

Predominantly two mechanisms with different origin control the interactions of the superconductivity with magnetic moments. One with electromagnetic origin is due to the interaction of Cooper pair with the magnetic field induced by the neighboring ferromagnet in the superconductor. The other of quantum origin is due to the exchange interaction acting on the Cooper pair as it enters ferromagnetic region. Under specific circumstances these mechanisms may either enhance or suppress superconductivity [50]. Taking electromagnetic interaction into account there may be

cases where the internal field produced by the ferromagnet compensates the external applied field at some regions of the FSH where the two components are directed in reverse directions. This results in the survival of superconductivity in these regions [51, 52]. Also there may be cases where the internal field adds up to the external field resulting in the suppression of superconductivity at some other regions [51, 52].

1.4.2.1 Field induced superconductivity

Fig. 1.6: Schematic illustration of field induced superconductivity. (a) The magnetic stray field B of the dots is comparable with the field of a magnetic dipole. (b) A magnetic field H applied in the z direction can be compensated by the dipole stray field between the dots, resulting in the conditions necessary for the observation of magnetic field-induced superconductivity (after Ref. [51]).

The appearance of magnetic field induced superconductivity (FIS) was first demonstrated in the 80's on $(\text{EuSn})\text{Mo}_6\text{S}_8$ [53, 54]. This unusual behavior was interpreted in terms of the Jaccarino-Peter effect [55], in which the exchange fields

from the paramagnetic ions compensate an applied magnetic field, so that the destructive action of the field is neutralized. The FIS has been realized for the first time in hybrid FM-SC nanostructured bilayers by Lange et al. [51] consisting of a superconducting film of Pb covered with magnetic dots of perpendicular anisotropy. The dipolar field of each dot produces magnetic field of opposite polarity under and outside the dots. As shown in Fig. 1.6, when an external field is applied normal to the surface of the film, a vector sum of the two fields can produce field-free region in the superconducting layer leading to an apparent enhancement of T_c .

1.4.2.2 Superconductivity near domain walls

The pair-breaking effect due to the exchange field that a Cooper pair experiences when it enters a ferromagnetic domain, strongly suppresses superconducting order. It was Matthias and Suhl [56] who first gave a satisfactory explanation for the observation of coexistence of superconductivity and ferromagnetism and the enhancement of the superconducting properties in dilute solid solution of rare earths in host superconductors. Recently, the influence of magnetic domain walls on superconductivity in FM-SC hybrids has been studied theoretically by Aladyshkin et al. [57] and Buzdin and Melnikov [58] for the case of magnetic film with perpendicular anisotropy. Their results show that the conditions for superconductivity are more favorable in the vicinity of domain walls rather than inside the domains of a ferromagnet. First experimental evidence on controlling the critical temperature (T_c) of FM-SC heterostructure by tuning the exchange field of the FM within the SC layer was reported by Kinsey et al. [59]. They observed that the suppression of T_c is minimized at the coercive field of the FM layer and argued that the domain structure formed by the FM layer near coercive field reduces the net exchange field in the SC layer. Recent study of Rusanov et al. [60] on $\text{Ni}_{0.80}\text{Fe}_{0.20}$ / Nb bilayers show how the domain state of $\text{Ni}_{0.80}\text{Fe}_{0.20}$ influences superconductivity in the Nb layer.

They have argued that the pair breaking potential experienced by a Cooper pair is smaller when it samples different directions of the exchange field simultaneously, which happens when the domain wall is very thin.

Theoretical studies suggest that active control of the magnetization of the ferromagnetic layers in FM-SC-FM heterostructures can also be used to modify the superconductivity in the sandwiched SC layer. These approaches use a pair of ferromagnetic layers with antiparallel magnetizations at low field and parallel at high field. When the two layers are aligned antiparallel, the exchange interaction and thereby the pair breaking potential is reduced leading to an enhancement in T_c [59]. Alternatively, by introducing two magnetic layers of different coercivity, the magnetic domain structure can be controlled selectively. A relative shift between the domain structure of the FM layers may result in positions in the superconductor where the stray field is close to zero, and hence, nucleation of superconductivity can be realized at these positions [61]. Gillijns et al. have found evidence for domain wall superconductivity in trilayer FM-SC-FM structures for different magnetic domain patterns. They have used superconducting Nb film sandwiched between two ferromagnetic Co/Pd multilayered films. Electrical resistivity measurements were carried out in different magnetic states of the top and bottom FM layers as a function of temperature and external magnetic field. The observed reentrant behavior of superconductivity in the low field limit has been explained in terms of broadening of domain walls due to a relative shift between the two domain structures.

Recently, domain wall superconductivity has been seen by Yang et al. [62] in an FM-SC hybrid consisting of Nb film deposited on single-crystal of $\text{BaFe}_{12}\text{O}_{19}$ which orders ferromagnetically at ≈ 1100 K. They observed that superconducting transition temperature of Nb increases with increasing external magnetic field until it reaches the saturation field of $\text{BaFe}_{12}\text{O}_{19}$. The enhanced superconductivity and pronounced hysteresis effects in field dependence resistance measurements have been

attributed to both the compensation of the external field by the stray field of the domains and the evolution of the domain structure with field.

1.4.3 NbN as a test system

We have selected NbN as a test system to study the effects of the planar and nanopatterned thin films of ferromagnetic CoPt on the superconducting state of strong type-II superconductor. NbN is particularly suitable for such studies because of its high transition temperature ($T_c \approx 16$ K) and large upper critical field ($H_{c2} > 250$ kOe) and its compatibility of growth with CoPt. It has been found that thin films of NbN with fairly high critical temperature can be fabricated at relatively low growth temperatures [63]. This feature make it possible to integrate NbN into hybrid structures without much interdiffusion at its interface with the ferromagnetic layer. In the following we summarize some key properties of niobium nitride.

1.4.3.1 Crystallographic structure

NbN has been investigated extensively in the past. While the group IV transition metal nitrides mainly crystallize in the cubic NaCl structure (B1 type), those of group V and VI occur as several phases with wide stoichiometric compositions. Many phases have been reported in the literature for equiatomic niobium nitride. These are; the cubic fcc δ -NbN (B1 type), the hexagonal δ' -NbN (NiAs type), the hexagonal CW type and hcp AsTi type [64]. The calculated and experimental lattice parameters of these phases are given in the literature [64]. Recently, an extensive study on sputtered NbN_x films with ($0.61 \leq x \leq 1.06$) under varied substrate temperature and nitrogen partial pressure has been reported by Benkahoul et al. [65]. They observed that the films deposited at room temperature form pure cubic δ - NbN_x phase for $0.61 \leq x \leq 0.98$, while those with $0.98 \leq x \leq 1.06$ are mixed phase consisting of hexagonal δ' -NbN and cubic δ -NbN phases.

Fig. 1.7: Crystal structures of the (a) rocksalt type NbN and (b) NbN structure with $Pm\bar{3}m$ symmetry.

Among these nitrides, only the δ -NbN has been extensively studied in past because of its superconducting and exceptional mechanical properties. This is a highly refractory material with bulk superconducting transition temperature of ≈ 16 K. A new superconducting phase has been reported for the first time by Treece et al. [66] in mid 90's. They observed that films grown by PLD at higher deposition temperatures condense in a primitive cubic structure with $Pm\bar{3}m$ symmetry [66]. The superconducting critical temperature of these films was 16.4 K and the lattice parameter 4.442 \AA , which is slightly larger than the lattice parameter of the dominant rocksalt structure (4.374 \AA). X-ray diffraction patterns and oscillation photographs from this films led to the conclusion that this new phase of NbN (Fig. 1.7(b)) is isomorphic with the primitive cubic structure of NbO and deviates from its common rocksalt structure (Fig. 1.7(a)) with 25 % vacancy-ordered rocksalt structure with vacancies at $(0,0,0)$ and $(1/2,1/2,1/2)$ [64]. Surprisingly, this primitive cubic phase is not observed in sputtered films of NbN.

1.4.3.2 Superconductivity in NbN

Niobium nitride is a strong coupling BCS superconductor with an energy gap close to 5 meV. The magnetic penetration depth (λ) in this group V nitride is close to 200 nm and the coherence length (ξ) is < 5 nm. In thin film of NbN the superconducting properties have been found to be highly dependent on their microstructure.

Commonly, NbN is deposited by reactive sputtering or Pulsed Laser Ablation of a high purity metallic Nb target in a nitrogen ambient. In both modes of deposition, the decisive parameters are the deposition temperature and nitrogen partial pressure. Films grown at reduced substrate temperatures (< 90 °C) show a granular microstructure with randomly oriented grains of dimension ~ 5 nm [63]. The nitrogen partial pressure during deposition is one of the most important factors which controls the grain-boundary resistance and hence the effective coupling between neighboring grains. Recently Senapati et al. demonstrated that PLD films grown under excessive nitrogen partial pressure invariably show a residual resistivity ratio < 1 [67]. It has been observed that the normal state transport as well as superconducting properties of NbN are greatly influenced by the degree of crystallinity. For instance, unlike single crystal films, the normal state resistivity of polycrystalline films can vary from 100 to 2000 $\mu\Omega$ -cm although the T_c remains the same. The higher normal-state resistivity is believed to arise primarily from an activated mechanism of inter-grain conduction across the insulating grain boundaries [68].

The normal state transport behavior of NbN provides insight into the nature of the superconducting state. For polycrystalline film for high resistivity the superconducting state can be more appropriately modeled as Josephson-coupled superconducting grains [69]. The critical current density under this model can be expressed in terms of the Ambegaoker-Baratoff relation with a typical temperature dependence of the form $J \sim (1 - T/T_c)$ close to T_c . The grain-boundary resistance along

with the grain-size and intra-grain purity of the NbN phase (which determines the Ginzburg-Landau coherence length $\xi_{GL}(T)$ [70]) play an important role in setting the macroscopic superconducting properties of the polycrystalline films. For example, unlike single crystal the upper critical field is commonly found to be anisotropic in polycrystalline films despite the well known cubic (B1; NaCl) crystal structure of this material.

1.5 Motivation for the present work

Studies of the correlation between crystallographic as well as morphological structure and magnetic coercivity of CoPt and FePt alloy films have been of considerable interest in recent years. Such research has been motivated primarily by the ever-increasing needs of the magnetic data recording industry for higher packing density combined with chemical stability of the storage medium which are met by CoPt and FePt alloys. A higher packing density naturally implies a much smaller magnetic entity. However, as the size of the grains becomes small enough to form single-domains, the magnetic response of the granular sample differs significantly from that in the bulk. A controlled growth of nanoparticles and epitaxial films of these alloys, and studies of magnetization and the process of its reversal in such structures is, therefore, an essential direction of research.

The perpendicular magnetic anisotropy in CoPt and FePt films also makes them promising for flux pinning in superconductors. An important issue that needs to be considered while addressing the physics of SC-FM-SC and FM-SC-FM heterostructures is the difference in the crystallographic structure and the degree of strain in the top and bottom SC or FM layers, and interdiffusion at interfaces which could impart different physical properties to the top and bottom layers. Thus far most of the studies in this area have been carried out on heterostructures of elemental superconductors such as Nb and Pb deposited on in-plane as well as high coercivity

perpendicular anisotropy media [46, 48, 51, 52, 57, 61, 71, 72]. It is expected that the competition between the SC and FM orders will have a different flavor if hard superconductors characterized by a short coherence length and large magnetic penetration depth are used. The nature of magnetic layers is also not less important as field-enhanced superconductivity and vortex pinning depend greatly on the domain structure and dynamics of domain wall motion in the magnetic layer [73].

The other issue related to the field-induced changes in the critical temperature is the fact that the field-free regions produced by the dipolar field are not homogeneous in these systems [52]. Also it is not clear whether superconductivity actually survives in areas above (or below) the magnetic dots because of the small upper critical field of the elemental superconductors and the strong magnetization of the dots. The global superconducting order parameter in these SC-FM hybrids is highly inhomogeneous irrespective of the orientation of magnetization. The field-temperature (H-T) phase diagram of a granular superconductor is quite rich and has been investigated for composite films [74], high T_c ceramics [75] and Josephson-junction arrays [76]. It is therefore possible that some of the novel effects seen in FM-SC hybrids could be a consequence of this granularity which is facilitated by the magnetic order.

The above discussion has broadly outlined the scope of the present thesis. The motivation behind the present study is twofold;

First: To understand the effects of various deposition conditions on morphological, crystallographic and magnetic characteristics of equiatomic CoPt, and to investigate the relationship between high coercivity and chemical ordering.

Second: To understand some of the basic aspects of the interplay between superconductivity and magnetism in CoPt/NbN bilayer systems, and how tailored granularity of the superconducting and magnetic order parameters affect the response of the combined system.

The layout of the thesis is as follows:

Chapter 1 is an introduction to the basic concepts of magnetism and its evolution with chemical ordering in binary cobalt-platinum alloys. Crystallographic structure and the superconducting phase of NbN are discussed with a brief review on granularity aspects of superconducting NbN. The interplay of superconductivity and magnetism and its repercussion on superconductivity in hybrid structures have been reviewed. This chapter concludes with the identification of some critical issues of magnetism in CoPt and superconductivity in NbN/CoPt hybrids which are addressed in the subsequent chapters.

Chapter 2 presents a detailed layout of the various experimental procedures used in this thesis. In the first few sections we briefly explore the basic mechanism and advantages and drawbacks of the PLD technique. The concept of Pulsed Laser Ablation in Aqueous Medium (PLAAM) to fabricate colloidal solutions of metal and alloy nanoparticles is also introduced. In section 2.5 we have discussed Ar⁺ ion milling and maskless Focused Ion Beam (FIB) techniques for patterning of samples and to create 2-dimensional array of CoPt islands. Two-axis X-ray powder diffractometer for structural characterization is described thereafter. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM), Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) and Magnetic Force Microscopy (MFM) have been introduced in the subsequent sections. We have used these techniques for investigation of topography and morphology of film surfaces and for imaging of magnetic domains. A Superconducting Quantum Interference Device (SQUID) based magnetometer, which was used for measurements of magnetization and magnetic relaxation, is introduced in section 2.8. The dynamics of vortices in NbN/CoPt heterostructures was investigated using a miniature Hall-probe based ac susceptometer. A brief

discussion of this technique is presented in section 2.9. Finally, the standard four probe technique for measurements of resistivity, magnetoresistance and critical current density is briefed in section 2.10.

Chapter 3 presents synthesis of CoPt nanoparticles dispersed in surfactant polymer matrix using Pulsed Laser Ablation in Aqueous Medium (PLAAM). The key advantage of this technique is in synthesis of multielemental nanoparticles of a desired stoichiometry without the use of hazardous chemicals. Studies of the magnetization dynamics of nanoparticles of the disordered low temperature fcc phase of CoPt alloy are reported. The magnetization dynamics of these particles is examined in the framework of superparamagnetic blocking phenomenon based on log-normal size distribution. Our analysis reveals, in accordance with electron microscopy results, two size distributions which peak at 1.3 nm and 5.9 nm. The magnetic anisotropy energy of these particles is 0.9×10^6 J/m³ and 0.1×10^6 J/m³ respectively.

Chapter 4 deals with strained epitaxial CoPt films grown using PLD on single crystal substrates of different lattice parameter. The choice of different substrates allows tuning of the strain and hence the surface morphology of the films, which also depends on process parameters such as deposition temperature and growth rate, in addition to the degree of lattice match with the substrate. We note that the role of lattice mismatch in controlling the growth morphology of these films is important only when the flux of adatoms on the substrate is kept low. At high flux densities, kinetic effects suppress the morphological features which might have evolved due to an imbalance of strain and interfacial energies of the film. The best c-axis oriented epitaxial L1₀ CoPt thin films display a coercive field as high as ≈ 30 kOe and anisotropy energy density of $\sim 4.62 \times 10^6$ J/m³ at ambient temperature.

Chapter 5 discusses the effect of strain due to lattice mismatch and proximity-effect on superconductivity in CoPt/NbN bilayers. Two different bilayer systems with reversed deposition sequence are grown on MgO (001) substrates. It is observed that the epitaxial growth is greatly affected by the interfacial strain, particularly in the NbN-CoPt/MgO system where it makes the NbN film to adopt a strain-induced granular structure, which has interesting repercussions on superconductivity. Overall suppression of superconductivity as observed from magnetization and transport critical current measurements in this system compared to the other bilayer geometry suggests perturbation in the electronic structure although no direct evidence of suppressed superconducting order parameter is observed from susceptibility measurements.

Chapter 6 discusses superconductivity in CoPt/NbN bilayers consisting of nanoengineered artificial structures. Here we argue that in FM-SC systems where the FM domains/islands produce spatial inhomogeneities of the SC order parameter, the observed FIS can derive significant contribution from different mobilities of the magnetic flux identified by two distinct critical states in the inhomogeneous superconductor. Our experiments on nanoengineered bilayers of ferromagnetic CoPt and superconducting NbN where CoPt/NbN islands are separated by a granular NbN, lend support to this alternative explanation of FIS in certain class of FM-SC hybrids.

Chapter 7 presents a brief summary of important results of our experiments on colloids and thin films of equiatomic CoPt alloy, and magnetic coupling and induced superconductivity in CoPt/NbN bilayers. Here we also identify some issues which are potentially interesting for further studies.

2. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

2.1 Introduction

The working principle of the experimental techniques used to carry out the present research are described in this chapter. In the first few sections we explore the basic mechanism and, advantages and drawbacks of the Pulsed Laser Deposition (PLD) technique. The concept of Pulsed Laser Ablation in Aqueous Medium (PLAAM) to synthesize colloidal solutions of metal and alloy nanoparticles is also introduced. Section 2.5 of this chapter is devoted to patterning of sample geometry and to create 2D-organized arrays of CoPt islands of submicron size. The techniques used here include Ar⁺ ion milling and Focused Ion Beam (FIB) lithography. Structural characterization of thin films and bilayers was carried out using two-axis X-ray powder diffractometer, which has been discussed in section 2.6. In section 2.7 we introduce Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM), Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) and Magnetic Force Microscopy (MFM). We have used these techniques to investigate surface topography, morphology and local magnetic domain structures of our films. Measurements of magnetization and magnetic relaxation were carried out using a Superconducting Quantum Interference Device (SQUID) based magnetometer. The SQUID magnetometer has been introduced in section 2.8. For the measurements of vortex dynamics and dissipation in NbN superconducting films, and NbN/CoPt bilayers we have used a miniature home made Hall-probe based susceptometer. A brief discussion on this technique is given in section 2.9. Standard four probe method used for measurements of resistivity, mag-

netoresistance and critical current density down to 4.2 K in a customized closed-cycle refrigerator based setup has been presented in section 2.10.

2.2 Pulsed Laser Deposition

The Pulsed Laser Deposition (PLD) technique has emerged as a powerful tool for thin film growth in recent years. It has been particularly useful in growing thin films of complex, multi-component materials without any loss of stoichiometry, which is a major advantage over other physical vapor deposition techniques. Under carefully controlled conditions, thin films of organic polymers have also been fabricated using PLD. The success in stoichiometric transfer of complex materials from target to the substrate lies in the mechanism of material ablation from a solid target by short ultraviolet (UV) laser pulses of high energy density. This versatile technique also offers a multitude of easily tunable parameters e.g. pulse energy density, pulse rate and wide variability of background pressure during deposition, which is not possible with other physical vapor deposition methods.

2.2.1 Principles

Pulsed Laser Deposition relies on targeting a solid source of the desired stoichiometry with focused, high energy density (typically a few J/cm^2) laser pulses of duration 100 fs to 50 ns. A schematic illustration of the PLD process is shown in Fig. 2.2. The dynamics of interaction between the target and laser pulse varies depending on the width of the pulse, its energy density and physical properties of the target. In case of femtosecond laser pulses, for example, electronic excitations in the target dominate role and result in direct solid-vapor or solid-plasma transitions [78–80]. Due to the very short time involved in this process, heat transfer into the target is extremely small and damages to the target are minimal [81–83]. On the other hand, nanosecond laser pulses allow more time for the incident energy to spread

over a larger volume of the target material. Consequently, the ablation process is controlled by conduction and thermal diffusion in the target.

The nature of target also plays an important role here. A highly conducting target absorbs most of the incident electromagnetic energy in a very thin layer at the surface (skin depth) and dissipates the heat energy over a much larger length scale governed by the thermal diffusion length. As a result, the ablation efficiency is reduced considerably for the combination of metallic targets and longer (nsec) laser pulses [81–84]. On the other hand, ceramic targets with thermal diffusion length much smaller than the skin depth, the incident energy is absorbed and dissipated over the same length scale (skin depth), which is independent of the pulse duration.

In general, the extremely short time scale laser pulse-target interaction prohibits complete dissipation of the large amount of incident energy into the bulk of the target. Consequently, the exposed spot on the target surface superheats locally and explodes out carrying a stoichiometric plasma of the target material. The ionized plasma (plume) expands into the deposition chamber, and can be condensed on a substrate placed at a suitable distance. Several parameters like the laser fluence, the substrate temperature, the position of the substrate with respect to the plume, and the reactivity as well as pressure of the ambient gas are used to tune the film growth. The background gas can either be reactive such as O_2 in the case of oxide films, reducing such as Ar/H_2 when depositing superconducting MgB_2 films, or passive such as Ar . The optimal values of these parameters depend on the material to be ablated. The effects of such tunable parameters on the growth of the film are discussed in the following section.

2.2.2 Tunable parameters and their effects

2.2.2.1 Laser fluence

The most important aspect of PLD is the process of material removal from the target which efficiently transfers the stoichiometry from the target to the substrate. A certain threshold laser fluence is crucial for this process. The threshold fluence shows a wide variation [79, 82, 85] from material to material, due to the dependence of laser-target interaction on the wavelength, pulse duration, reflectivity and porosity of the target. The fluence has a significant effect on the shape, size, and quality of the plume. As the fluence increases above the threshold value, the ionic species in the resulting plume acquire more kinetic energy and the visible tail of the plume elongates. The extent of the visible plume is decisive in positioning of the substrate to ensure effective condensation of the ablated material, for the kinetic energy of the ionic species might be enough to sputter the surface of the substrate when placed inside the visible plume. At very high fluence, formation of defects and cracks on the target surface can considerably modify the shape and angle of the extracted plume.

The size of the laser spot on the target along with the pulse energy determines the effective laser fluence. Large spot-size can affect the plume uniformity due to non-uniform energy density over different regions of the spot. The gaussian energy profile of the beam from most of the commercial lasers is an important issue in this regard. Similarly, very small spot-size results in low ablation efficiency and splashing (ejection of droplets from the target). For this reason, optimization of the spot size in conjunction with the pulse energy plays a vital role in the quality of the film.

In addition, the angular distribution of the plume in the substrate plane may change when the target-substrate distance is large, particularly when the deposition is carried out in a gas environment. [86].

2.2.2.2 Ambient gas environment

After the formation at the surface of the target, the plume expands through the deposition chamber. During this expansion phase, the dynamics of the plume is largely dependent on the pressure and nature of the gas in deposition chamber. The background gas in the chamber helps to homogenize the plume and mark the visible edges of the plume by characteristic colors. Since the stoichiometry of the plume is highly directional in vacuum, the presence of a background gas improves its homogeneity by multiple scattering of the ablated atoms. The background gas also provides a suitable reactive environment at the substrate, when needed. For example, most of the high T_c ceramic superconductors are grown in a controlled oxygen environment to obtain the required oxygen rich, superconducting phase.

2.2.3 Film nucleation and growth dynamics: influence of deposition parameters

Apart from the above factors, fine tuning of the film growth process is achieved by optimization of substrate temperature, target-substrate distance, and the pulse repetition rate. The latter two parameters determine the rate of arrival of the atomic components at the substrate and substrate temperature regulates the rearrangement of these atomic components on the surface. The nucleation of film consisting of atom clusters on a substrate involve several atomic processes which are presented in Fig. 2.1. The selection of one particular growth mode by a substrate-film system depends on the thermodynamics related to the surface and interface energies, and the balance between growth and dissolution processes for a given cluster is determined by the total free energy of the film-substrate-vapor system. The film growth can be broadly divided into four different modes considering the general theory of film nucleation, and depending on how the atoms arrange themselves on the sub-

strate: (i) three-dimensional islands growth (Volmer-Weber), (ii) two-dimensional formation of full monolayers (Frank-van der Merwe), (iii) two-dimensional growth of full monolayers followed by nucleation and growth of three-dimensional islands (Stranski-Krastinov), and the so-called (iv) step-flow growth where the film follows the step/terrace structures of the substrate [87–89].

Fig. 2.1: Schematic diagram of atomic processes in the nucleation of three dimensional clusters of deposited film atoms on a substrate surface (after [87]).

In the three-dimensional growth mode, the atoms incident on the substrate surface form clusters which start to grow in size without touching each other such that the resulting film consists of large but separate islands of atoms. In general a cluster will grow if the derivative of the free energy with respect to the number of atoms in it is negative [87]. The formation of a stable cluster can also be described in terms of surface energies. If the sum of the surface energies in the cluster-vapor and substrate-cluster interfaces is larger than the corresponding surface energy for the

substrate-vapor interface, the film will grow three-dimensionally [87].

If the above mentioned inequality for the surface energies is not satisfied, it will be energetically more favorable for the film to grow as a single layer leading to full monolayer formation on the substrate. Two-dimensional growth also involves the nucleation and growth of islands with one monolayer thick which eventually coalesce before significant clustering. Layer-by-layer type film growth results in epitaxial films with an atomically smooth surface.

The basic sequence of Stranski-Krastinov growth mode is that atoms arriving at substrate initially form few complete monolayers followed by nucleation of three-dimensional clusters. This effect, mainly resulting from increased stress with increasing layer thickness is typically observed in systems where stress due to improper lattice match between the film and the substrate are involved. Strong chemical bonding between the substrate and the film is also found to be an important factor that alters the surface energy of the initial layer with increasing thickness [87].

The fourth type of growth, i.e, the step-flow growth can be viewed, in general, as heterogeneous nucleation which involves, for instance, atomic steps, point defects, and dislocations in the substrate providing low-energy sites which favor nucleation and growth. The onset of this growth mode again depends on various process parameters. While the rate of nucleation and nuclei density are controlled by the distribution of low-energy sites at low supersaturation, sufficiently high supersaturation may trigger homogeneous nucleation that alters the growth mode leading to formation of either three-dimensional clusters or a two-dimensional full monolayer [87]. Also, as the thickness of the film increases, there is a possibility that the growth mode changes to form three-dimensional clusters [88, 89].

2.2.4 Drawbacks

Although PLD is a versatile deposition technique, it still suffers from several major drawbacks. The most serious one is the formation of particulates on the film leading to a rough surface. Particulates can arrive as such from the target or can cluster during the expansion of the plume. Several methods have been proposed to tackle this issue, including off-axis laser-ablation geometry [90], negative biasing of the substrate [91], and use of velocity filters in the plume path [92].

Another issue of concern is the low angular range of compositional uniformity, which results largely due to the highly directional nature of the plume. This is a major challenge for large area film deposition. Interestingly however, large area depositions have been reported using a technique that utilizes a rotating substrate and a large-diameter counter rotating target in conjunction with a rastered laser beam and large target-to-substrate distance [93]. Another method successfully employed for large area PLD uses both substrate rotation and computer-controlled substrate translation.

In the case of PLD with Gaussian beams, only the central part of the beam leads to stoichiometric ablation whereas the beam edges may ablate elements without preserving the stoichiometry of the target materials. This issue is of great importance since the beam profile of an excimer laser depends very critically on the alignment of the optics, the voltage of the discharge, and it varies with the age of the gas fill. Therefore, changes can occur even during a single growth run. These variations result in asymmetries of the plume, which in turn strongly influences film growth [94–96]. However, problems related to the inherent Gaussian intensity distribution of the laser pulses can be improved by using a beam shaping/homogenizing system which controls the distribution of the energy density [95, 96].

Fig. 2.2: Vapor phase Pulsed Laser Deposition (PLD) facility in our laboratory.

2.3 Vapor phase PLD

2.3.1 The deposition chamber

In the following a detailed description of the vapor phase PLD setup used in our laboratory is presented. A photograph of the system and its important accessories are shown in Fig. 2.2 and Fig. 2.3. The depositions have been carried out in a turbo-molecular pump based 12-inch-diameter vacuum chamber whose base pressure can be lowered down to 1×10^{-6} Torr. A carousel-type holder, designed for three targets

Fig. 2.3: Main components of PLD facility: (a) multi-target carousel, (b) substrate heater and (c) deposition chamber (Courtesy Excel Instruments).

and facilitated with rastering scan was used. The substrate heater was designed to maintain constant temperatures up to $850\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. To ensure a proper thermal contact between the holder surface and substrate during the depositions, the latter were glued to the heater base with silver paint.

2.3.2 The excimer laser source

The name excimer comes from excited dimer. The excimer is a gas laser system that emits pulses of light with a duration of 10 to 100 ns in the ultraviolet (UV) spectral range. There are number of excimer lasers of different wavelength ranging from 150 to 351 nm available commercially. The highest gain system for electrically discharged pumped excimer lasers is a krypton-fluoride (KrF) based system and is most popular amongst the PLD community [97].

In KrF excimer lasers, the upper laser level is an ionically bound charge transfer state of the 2P rare gas positive ion (Kr^+) and the 1S halogen negative ion (F^-). The upper laser level is populated by a three-body collision involving Kr^+ , F^- , and a third collision partner (called buffer gas, for example Ne or He). While there is a minimum in the potential energy curve in the upper state it is still rather unstable. The excited KrF^* molecule decays via spontaneous emission of a photon after several nanoseconds into Kr and F. These form the ground state which is covalently bonded and consists of separate Kr and F atoms for large inter-nuclear separations. The components Kr and F atoms are then available for another excitation cycle [98].

In our PLD system the laser pulses are produced by a Lambda Physik COMPex-Pro KrF excimer laser which lases at 248 nm with a pulse width of 20-30 nsec. The maximum pulse energy obtained with a discharge voltage of 27 kV is ≈ 750 mJ. The dimensions of the nearly rectangular transverse output profile of the beam are $24 \times 6 - 12$ mm². In the present beam shaping and guiding system, the pulses pass through a $22 \times 6 - 12$ mm² aperture (depending on the age of the gas fill), after which they are imaged with a plano-convex lens ($f = 300$ mm) onto the target surface. The intensity distribution on the target has an excellent uniformity across the typical $7 - 8$ mm² spot area.

2.3.3 Deposition of thin films and bilayer structures of CoPt and NbN using vapor phase PLD

2.3.3.1 Target preparation

Alloy ingots with composition CoPt were prepared from 99.9 % pure cobalt and platinum by arc melting in an atmosphere of pure (99.99 %) argon. The as-arc-melted alloys were cast in the form of a thin disc of about 5 mm thick and 5 mm radius. The sample was vacuum sealed in a quartz tube, homogenized at 900 °C, which is above the disorder-order transition temperature of CoPt, and then quenched. For preparation of NbN films reactive PLD was used with 20×10×2 mm³ high purity (99.9 %) niobium plate as target.

2.3.3.2 Deposition conditions

Only the small central region of the plume, which safely accommodates three 3 × 3 mm² substrates on the heater plane, was used to ensure homogeneity over the entire film. In most of the experiments, the target-substrate distance was fixed to approximately 40 mm. In our experiments, the pulse energy on the PLD target was maintained at 200 - 250 mJ, laser fluence ranged from 2.5 to 4 J/cm² for CoPt and ≈ 7.2 J/cm² for NbN, the substrate temperatures were varied between 600 and 800 °C and the laser-pulse repetition rate was 10 Hz. Prior to deposition of the films, the chamber was evacuated to 1×10⁻⁶ Torr base pressure after several rounds of flushing with ultra high purity (99.9999 %) N₂. Titanium sublimation pump was used afterwards to pump out chemically reactive species. While for the CoPt layers the chamber was maintained at 50 mTorr pressure of N₂, the deposition pressure was optimized to ~ 80 mTorr for the best quality NbN layers [67]. It is important to mention here that the deposition of CoPt layers was carried out in nitrogen atmosphere (used as buffer) to reduce particulate density on the film surface. The

buffer gas was pumped out of the chamber on completion of film deposition to ensure that no stable nitrides of cobalt are formed when the film is cooled from the growth temperature (≥ 600 °C). The optimum deposition parameters will be discussed in more detail in subsequent chapters.

2.4 Pulsed Laser Ablation in Aqueous Medium (PLAAM)

In the last few decades, a great deal of research interest has generated in metallic nanostructured materials due to their unusual electronic, optical, magnetic, and chemical properties which are different from those in the bulk form [99]. Among these, metallic colloids are of special interest owing to their potential technological applications in biosensors, drug delivery systems, biological labels, and catalysis [100]. However, these potential applications require a precise control over the structure, chemical composition, and grain size of metallic particles in the colloids [101]. Therefore, it is important to develop a technique that can synthesize stable nanoparticles with narrow size distribution.

The usual techniques for synthesizing metallic colloids include mechanical milling, solution chemistry, vapor-phase synthesis, and sol-gel. Recently, a new method was developed to synthesize metallic colloid which uses Pulsed Laser Ablation of metal target in a liquid medium [81]. Compared to chemical synthesis, the advantages of this method are the simplicity of the procedure and absence of chemical reagents in solution. Pulsed Laser Ablation has also appeared to be the most flexible and promising technique because it allows ablation of almost all kinds of materials due to the ultra-high energy density associated with the laser beam. Moreover, one can control the growth simply by tuning the process parameters like irradiation time, duration, energy density, wavelength, etc. [102].

2.4.1 Ablation efficiency: aqueous phase laser ablation

2.4.1.1 Effects of laser wavelength

The relation between the ablation efficiency and laser wavelength in liquid [103, 104] is different from that observed in vapor phase systems where it is higher at shorter wavelengths [105]. Usually the low ablation efficiency of metal targets is attributed to their high reflectivity and to thermal losses due to their high thermal conductivity. In addition to these mechanisms of energy loss, in the aqueous phase ablation additional factors such as nonlinear absorption in the liquid [106] and confinement of the plasma plume also limit the efficiency. Another factor is the re-deposition of the emitted target species due to strong scattering from the high-density liquid above the target. Therefore, large-scale production of nanoparticles is a major challenge for the PLAAM technique.

2.4.1.2 Effects of self-absorption

It has been demonstrated that the particle size of silver colloids drops on increasing the number of irradiating laser pulses [104]. This phenomenon is explained in terms of self-absorption of laser pulses by colloidal particles in the solution. Tsuji et al. [104] have proposed two possible mechanisms for the self-absorption process: (1) inter-pulse self-absorption in which colloidal particles formed by former pulses absorb the following pulses, and (2), intra-pulse self-absorption, in which colloidal particles formed by former part of a laser pulse absorb later part of the same pulse. The latter is more prominent in the case of ablation using a nanosecond laser pulse. The absorbed energy of laser light can thermally excite the lattice of metal particles, leading to the fragmentation of the particles. Procházka et al. [107] and Mafuné et al. [101] showed that irradiation of colloidal solution with laser light significantly reduce the particle size of colloids due to fragmentation of particles.

2.4.1.3 Effects of dual pulse laser

Burakov et al. [108] demonstrated Pulsed Laser Ablation of metal samples in liquid environment by using a combination of two laser beams. They have shown that this technique promotes formation of size-selected nanoparticles with reduced dimensions. The size reduction is most effectively achieved under conditions of suitable temporal delays in firing of the first laser which causes ablation and the second laser beam which breakup the particles. Although the mechanism of laser-induced fragmentation is not fully understood, it can be argued that heating due to absorption of the laser energy by the particles, which causes melting and vaporization, leads to the fragmentation. Also disintegration of large particles into smaller ones because of their charging under laser pulse excitation and Coulomb explosion (discussed in ref. [109, 110]) can be responsible for the observed morphological changes. The second laser beam can also lead to formation of clusters under special circumstances. For example, additional excitation and ionization of atomic species by the second laser pulse can result in creation of ionic centers for initiation of condensation process resulting in formation of clusters, and their growth to the small sized nanoparticles inside the plume [108].

2.4.2 The ablation setup

A schematic diagram of the PLAAM setup is shown in Fig. 2.4. It consists of a target platform on which the target of desired material is mounted. A mechanical arrangement moves the platform back and forth with a speed of 0.3 mm/sec so that the laser beam scans the target surface continuously. This arrangement provides uniform ablation of the target and avoids laser irradiation at a particular place. As shown in the figure, the target holder assembly is suspended horizontally in a liquid bath. Beam of pulsed Nd:YAG laser (pulse width ~ 6 nsec) was used to irradiate the target from the top. A convex lens with a focal length of 200 mm was used to

Fig. 2.4: Left panel shows a schematic of the Pulsed Laser Ablation in Aqueous Medium (PLAAM) process. Right panel shows the operation of PLAAM.

focus the laser beam down to a spot of ~ 1 mm diameter onto the liquid surface. The solutions were stirred during ablation with a magnetic stirrer.

2.4.3 The source Nd:YAG laser

Nd:YAG laser is a solid-state system in which neodymium ions serve as active medium and are present as impurities in the YAG (yttrium-aluminum-garnet) host - a synthetic crystal with a garnet-like structure. Nd:YAG lasers are optically pumped using flashlamps or laser diodes. By flashing a rare gas filled lamp in close proximity with the Nd:YAG laser rod, some of the broadband radiation from the lamp is absorbed by the rod and is momentarily stored within the excited state of the neodymium ions. The excited (metastable) state of Nd^{3+} has a lifetime of about 250 μsec . Nd:YAG lasers operate in both pulsed and continuous mode. Pulsed Nd:YAG lasers are typically operated in the so called Q-switching mode: An optical switch is inserted in the laser cavity waiting for a maximum population inversion in the neodymium ions before it opens. Then the light wave can run through the cavity, depopulating the excited laser medium at maximum population inversion. The laser

output is comprised of infra-red photons that are essentially identical in phase and amplitude. Although Nd:YAG lasers typically emit light with a wavelength of 1064 nm, nonlinear crystals in combination with other optics can be used to generate wavelengths other than the fundamental one. They include 532 nm, 355 nm and 266 nm radiations. Dichroic optics can be used to separate output wavelengths.

In our experiments for aqueous phase ablation, a commercial Ultra CFR Nd:YAG laser from Quantel Big Sky was used. The laser was equipped with a temperature-controlled KTP doubler inside a nonlinear optics module to generate 532 nm radiation. The 532 nm radiation is then mixed with the residual 1064 nm radiation to produce 355 nm light. With the double bounce dichroic module, the system gives monochromatic 355 nm beam together with the combination of 1064 nm and 532 nm radiations which exit the laser head through separate output apertures.

2.4.4 Preparation of magnetic colloids using PLAAM technique

A plate of arc-melted $\text{Co}_{0.5}\text{Pt}_{0.5}$ alloy was irradiated with a focussed beam of pulsed Nd-YAG laser from the top. The laser was operated at 20 Hz with a combined energy density of 14 J/cm^2 at 1064 nm and 532 nm wavelengths. A light brown but clear solution, with no evidence of any sedimentation, was obtained after 25 minutes of ablation. In order to avoid agglomeration of particles, sodium dodecyl-sulfate (SDS) was added to the solution immediately after the ablation process and homogenized by ultrasonification for 10 minutes. The colloidal solution was concentrated through the process of vacuum evaporation of excess water to obtain the nanoparticles. The larger particles and agglomerates were separated subsequently through centrifugation at $\sim 3000 \text{ g}$ of the resultant solution for 15 minutes.

2.5 Sample patterning

2.5.1 Ar⁺ ion milling

Ion beam milling is a powerful technique used for lithography of thin films. The basic principle of ion milling involves bombarding a specimen with a beam of energetic (several hundreds of eV) ions or neutral atoms. The main components of our ion milling setup are (1) Discharge chamber - this is filled with a plasma composed of nearly equal number of electrons and ions, in a background of neutral atoms. (2) Cathode - a multi turn helical tungsten filament supported by two posts in the discharge chamber. The cathode is typically operated at a - 30 to 60 V relative to the anode for argon operation. (3) Accelerator system - consists of screen grid and accelerator grid. During the typical operation, the screen grid is maintained at cathode potential. The ions leaving to the discharge chamber are first accelerated and then decelerated. (4) Neutralizer - a multi-turn helical tungsten filament stretched across the edge of the ion beam. Electrons produced by the neutralizer provide space charge neutralization of the ion beam and prevent the build up of damaging surface potentials on the sample. The acceleration/deceleration mechanism mentioned above is to prevent neutralizer electrons to backstream through the accelerator system. (5) DC power supply - provides required voltage and current to the ion source. (6) Milling chamber - this is associated with vacuum pumping system. Although geometrical arrangements vary from system to system, but typically the sample stage either rotates or oscillates relative to the ion beam during the milling process. In our case a rotating sample stage facilitated with water cooling arrangement was used. The gas ambient of the deposition chamber was controlled by an electronic mass flow controller.

All bilayer samples for transport studies were patterned into a micron size bridge with Ar⁺ milling. The exact dimension of the bridge will be mentioned in detail

in chapter 5. Typical parameters in our case at argon gas pressure of 1×10^{-3} mbar inside the milling chamber are, Cathode filament current: ~ 2.2 A, discharge current: ~ 0.45 A, discharge voltage: ~ 58.5 V, beam current: $\sim 35 - 40$ A, beam voltage: $\sim 500 - 550$ V, accelerator current: ~ 1 mA, accelerator voltage: ~ 100 V, neutralizer emission current: $\sim 40 - 45$ A, neutralizer filament current: $\sim 1.8 - 1.9$ A, and average milling rate of NbN and CoPt films: $\sim 0.25 - 0.3$ nm/sec.

2.5.2 Focused Ion Beam (FIB)

Heavy ion beams are well suited for nanofabrication because they suffer very little scattering and have short penetration-depths in targets of variety of materials. For instance the mean in-depth free path of 30 keV Gallium ions in graphite is estimated to be 22.7 nm with a lateral straggling of 3.2 nm [111]. The another advantage of FIB is that instead of using resist layers for pattern definition such as in electron beam lithography process, the desired pattern may also be directly written on the surface. However, nanofabrication with scanned Focused Ion Beam (FIB) is a sequential process. It is therefore much slower than the parallel processes such as optical or electron beam lithography. Even then FIB technology has already found applications for relatively small operations on individual chips in IC manufacturing industry. FIB has also been used for fabrication of nanodevices in a research environment. Several examples of patterned magnetic layers using FIB can be found in the literature [112, 113].

In our case, this maskless technique is used to create a 2D arrays of submicron size squares of CoPt on the top of superconducting NbN films. A dual-beam Nova 600 NanoLab (FEI Company) instrument was used. The principle of a dual-beam instrument is described in more detail elsewhere [114]. The FEI FIB instrument was equipped with a liquid metal ion source providing the Ga ions. To minimize charging effects due to ion bombardment and the formation of secondary electrons,

the top surface of the film was grounded with silver epoxy. In order to achieve a sufficient small beam diameter and to maintain a slow etching rate, the experiments were carried out with the ion acceleration voltage and current set to 20 kV and 4 pA, respectively; this results in a nominal beam diameter of ~ 10 nm (FWHM). Furthermore, the focus and stigmatism of the ion beam were carefully adjusted and the etching rate was confirmed by drilling holes in the vicinity of the film under identical conditions. To image the samples in situ, the imaging functionality of the FEI workstation was used and will be presented in chapter 6.

2.6 Structural characterization

2.6.1 X-ray diffraction

X-ray Diffraction (XRD) is a powerful non-destructive technique for structural characterization of thin films, multilayers and superlattices. It provides information on crystallographic structure, phases, preferred crystal orientations (texture) and other structural parameters such as average grain size, crystallinity, strain and crystal defects.

X-ray measurements have been performed by using a two-axis powder diffractometer (Model-Seifert, XRD-3000 P) in a $\theta - 2\theta$ geometry. The diffractometer consists of a Cu - K_α source and a scintillation detector on the circumference of a vertical circle. A fixed sample stage is positioned at the center of the circle, which remains fixed while a goniometer assembly provides uniform rotation of both the source and detector. A few micron thick Ni foil is placed at the source window to filter out the K_β lines from K_α from the source radiation. The operation and control of the diffractometer, and recording of the detector output are performed through a computer aided software.

2.7 Surface topography, morphology and magnetic imaging

2.7.1 Scanning Electron Microscopy

Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) is one of the most sophisticated and widely used tools of modern science as it allows the study of both morphology and composition of biological and physical materials. By scanning an electron probe across a specimen, image resolution of about 5 nm of the morphology or topography of a specimen with great depth of field and different magnifications can be obtained. Compositional analysis of a material may also be obtained by monitoring X-rays produced by the electron-specimen interaction. SEM is often equipped with EDS (Energy Dispersive Spectrometer) or WDS (Wavelength Dispersive Spectrometer) to chemically characterize the materials for quantitative microanalysis.

SEM consists of an energetically well-defined, highly focused beam of electrons scanned across a sample. There are two different modes that have been available with SEM imaging depending on the energy of the electrons: Secondary Electron (SE) imaging and Back Scattered Electron (BSE) imaging. The Secondary Electron imaging works on the principle that electrons from the beam cause emission of secondary electrons the specimen with kinetic energy much lower than the energy of the incident electrons. Because of the low energies and low penetration depth, it is possible to attain high magnifications and high resolutions with the secondary electrons imaging technique. Back Scattered Electron (BSE) imaging, on the other hand, detects high-energy electrons which backscatter quasi-elastically off the sample. BSE originate not only from the surface but also from a certain depth within the sample, depending on its composition and on the energies of the primary beam electrons. BSE, when collected by appropriate detector, can also provide a contrast related to the chemical composition of selected area of the sample.

EDS detects X-rays from the sample excited by the highly focused, high-energy

primary electron beam from the sample. When the high-energy electrons interact with the atoms of material they generate characteristic X-rays, which in turn are used for elemental analysis.

The surface morphology and composition of our samples were analyzed using a commercial Scanning Electron Microscope (FEI QUANTA 200 HV) in BSE mode and Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDS).

2.7.2 Transmission Electron Microscopy

Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM) is a powerful tool to probe crystallographic details and chemical composition of phases distributed on a very fine scale in a given microstructure. Convergent beam electron diffraction, nano or micro beam diffraction and selected area diffraction techniques have been used to obtain crystallographic information whereas structural information is obtained by High Resolution Electron Microscopy (HREM). While in the SEM, the specimen is scanned with a focused beam of electrons, specimens in the TEM are examined by passing the electron beam through them, revealing more information of the internal structure of specimens. As the electron beam passes through the specimen, some electrons are scattered whilst the remainder are focused by the objective lens either onto a phosphorescent screen or a CCD camera to form an image.

We have undertaken TEM measurements on our CoPt nanoparticles for characterization of surface morphology and particle size distribution using JEOL JEM-3010, 300 KV microscope facility available at JNCASR, Bangalore. Preparation of samples for TEM measurements will be discussed in chapter 4.

2.7.3 Scanning Probe Microscopy

Scanning Probe Microscopy (SPM) encompasses a family of techniques that measure surface topography and surface properties on the atomic scale [115]. Some of the

variants of SPMs are the Scanning Tunneling Microscope (STM), Atomic Force Microscope (AFM), Electric Force Microscope (EFM), Lateral Force Microscope (LFM), and Magnetic Force Microscope (MFM). They share the common use of a small microprobe, which is most often a microscopic tip that senses a minute portion of the object.

AFM, invented by Binnig et al. measures extremely small forces up to 10^{-12} - 10^{-8} N [116]. It also provides a general method for non-destructive surface profilometry at a resolution better than 10 nm and perhaps down to the atomic level. In the following section the three basic imaging types in AFM have been discussed in brief.

2.7.3.1 Contact mode AFM

It operates by scanning a tip attached to the end of a cantilever across the sample surface, making a physical contact with the sample, while monitoring the change in cantilever deflection with a two-sided photodetector. As the scanner moves in a raster pattern across the sample, the cantilever bends to accommodate changes in topography with atomic resolution. However, sometimes sample get damaged by the excessive tracking force exerted by the probe that arises due to the air capillary forces from the adsorbed fluid layer on the sample's surface during scanning.

2.7.3.2 Tapping mode AFM

It was developed by Q. Zhong et. al. in 1993 which eliminated the problems posed by contact mode AFM [117]. With the Tapping mode technique the cantilever is oscillated at or near its resonance frequency with amplitude ranging from 20 - 100 nm. The oscillation amplitude is set sufficiently high such that when the probe taps on the surface, the cantilever has sufficient restoring force to prevent the tip from getting trapped in the adsorbed fluid layer exerting electrostatic attraction with the

sample and the tip. The probe is then brought closer to the sample surface until it begins to tap intermittently. The amplitude of this oscillation scales in direct proportion to the average distance of the probe and the sample.

2.7.3.3 Non-Contact AFM

Contact and Tapping modes AFM involve touching the sample. In some applications, especially for fluid, this may not be possible as the tip might get trapped. For these samples it is more advantageous to employ a tip that does not touch the sample. This can be accomplished by oscillating the cantilever at a frequency slightly above the cantilever's resonance frequency with amplitude typically of a few nanometers. When the resonating tip is brought near the surface of the sample, its resonance frequency as well as amplitude of vibrations drop due to the attractive Van der Waals force between the samples and the tip. Thus, changes in the oscillation amplitude, and the corresponding change in resonant frequency of a cantilever can be used to measure changes in the force gradient, which reflects changes in the tip-to-sample spacing.

2.7.4 Magnetic Force Microscopy

Magnetic Force Microscopes (MFM) is a type of AFM that detects the magnetic fields produced by the sample. It utilizes a tapping mode AFM and its tip is usually composed of etched silicon sputter-coated with a ferromagnetic material. Surface image detection by MFM is based on the magnetic field emanating from the sample which is sensed by the tip. A sensitive deflection sensor is used to detect cantilever motion and hence the force or force gradient. To form an image, the sample to tip interaction's strength is mapped as a function of the position of the sample. Two types of information can be obtained in MFM imaging: topography of the surface, and the local magnetic structure of the sample. A two-pass method, which

is also known as lift mode method, is employed to collect and separate out the two information.

Magnetic Force Microscopy (MFM) and Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) measurements on our samples were performed at JNCASR, Bangalore, on thermally demagnetized samples. A multi-mode AFM with a Nanoscope IV controller (Digital Instruments, Santa Barbara) was used in the tapping mode at different lift heights to probe the magnetic domain structure. The MFM tip (CoCr coated Si) was magnetized vertically along the tip axis, thereby allowing detection of the perpendicular component of stray field emanating from the sample surface with a spatial resolution of ≈ 50 nm. Simultaneous sampling of magnetic and topographic images at different lift heights (even upto 120 nm) ruled out any topographical artifact presents in our MFM images.

2.8 DC magnetization

There are several other techniques available for magnetization measurements such as Torque Magnetometry, VSM, Faraday Balance and Magneto Optical Kerr Effect (MOKE). However, SQUID magnetometry is now the most widely used method, especially because of its extreme sensitivity and simplicity. We have used a commercial [Quantum Design MPMS XL-5] squid magnetometer. The specifications of MPMS XL-5 are summarized as follows: absolute sensitivity of magnetization: $< 1 \times 10^{-8}$ emu at 0.25 T and $\leq 2 \times 10^{-7}$ emu at 5 T, maximum field range of 5 T with field setting resolution of 0.1 Oe at 0.5 T and 1 Oe at 5 T, temperature range: 1.9 - 400 K. The principle mechanism is based on moving the sample through a set of superconducting detection coils, which are located outside the sample chamber and at the center of the superconducting magnet. As the sample moves through the coils, the magnetic moment of the sample induces an electric current in the detection coils. Because the detection coils, the connecting wires, and the SQUID

input coil form a closed superconducting loop, any change of magnetic flux in the detection coils produces a change in the persistent current in the detection circuit, which is proportional to the change in magnetic flux. Since the SQUID functions as a highly linear current-to-voltage convertor, the variations in the current in the detection coils produce corresponding variations in the SQUID output voltage which is proportional to the magnetic moment of sample.

Both in-plane and out-of-plane field orientations were used in these measurements and all data were corrected for the contribution of the substrates. The data were taken using the Reciprocating Sample Option (RSO) for improved sensitivity and measurement speed. Unlike DC measurements where the sample moves through the coils in discrete steps the RSO measurements are performed using a servo motor which rapidly oscillates the sample.

2.9 Ac susceptibility

A miniature home made Hall-probe based susceptometer [118] was used for measurements of linear and non linear dynamics of vortices in NbN superconducting films as well as in CoPt/NbN bilayers. The design of the susceptometer is based on a primary coil for excitation of the sample and a miniature Hall sensor (active area $25 \times 25 \mu\text{m}^2$) for sensing the resultant emf. The sample is mounted at the center of the drive coil with its plane perpendicular to the axis of the coil. The Hall sensor is placed in close contact with the sample surface, electrically separated by a very thin mica foil ($\sim 10 \mu\text{m}$). The coil, when driven with a low amplitude ac current, produces harmonic screening currents on the surface of the superconducting film. This, in turn produces a local magnetic induction opposite to the applied ac field. A voltage signal, proportional to the vector sum of the applied and induced magnetic field is picked-up by the Hall sensor. The voltage is then decomposed, with a lock-in amplifier, into an in-phase component (V') and a component in quadrature (V'')

with the reference ac signal. Following the procedure of Gilchrist and Konczykowski [119], the real and imaginary parts of ac-susceptibility are calculated from the relations $\chi' = T'_H - 1$ and $\chi'' = T''_H$ respectively. T'_H and T''_H are the real and imaginary parts of complex transmittivity defined as,

$$T'_H = \frac{[V'(T) - V'(T \ll T_c)]}{[V'(T \gg T_c) - V'(T \ll T_c)]} \quad (2.1)$$

$$T''_H = \frac{[-V''(T)]}{[V'(T \gg T_c) - V'(T \ll T_c)]} \quad (2.2)$$

Unlike the case of a secondary coil based susceptometer, the output signal in this case is independent of the frequency of excitation. The real part χ' (T) of the complex susceptibility χ (T) = χ' (T) + $i\chi''$ (T) corresponds to the shielding effects, while the imaginary part χ'' (T) is connected to the energy dissipation in the material.

2.10 DC transport

Measurements of resistivity, magnetoresistance and critical current density were carried out in a customized low temperature measurement system based on a close-cycle refrigerator (Advanced Research Systems inc.). This system allows uninterrupted measurements down to 4.2 K. The same refrigerator was used for AC susceptibility measurements mentioned above. The cold head of the refrigerator is placed between the pole pieces of an electromagnet which is capable of producing 3500 G field. The magnet is attached with a stepper motor. The use of a worm gear assembly allowed a precision of 0.05 degree in rotation of the magnet. A detachable sample platform, fabricated from oxygen free high conductivity (OFHC) copper, was mounted on the cold-head of the refrigerator. The stage was equipped with two RuO₂ resistive

sensors for accurate temperature measurement and control. Samples were glued to the stage using Apiezone-N grease, which provides excellent thermal contact with the base. Measurements were performed using the standard four terminal geometry. Electrical contacts on the samples were made by soldering 25 micron gold wires with indium on evaporated silver contact pads.

3. MAGNETIC RELAXATION AND SUPERPARAMAGNETISM OF CoPt NANOPARTICLES

3.1 Introduction

Magnetic nanoparticles have attracted considerable attention in recent years because of their technological applications in areas such as high density data storage, ferrofluid mechanics, and biomedical/drug delivery systems [120–122]. These applications are driven by the unique magnetic behavior of the individual nanoparticles. Since a large fraction of atoms in a nanoparticle is on the surface, a different physiochemical environment of these atoms influences magnetic properties of magnetic nanoparticles in a non-trivial manner [123]. Additionally, the presence of random anisotropies and competing interparticle interactions in an assembly of particles make studies of magnetism in nanoparticles an interesting topic for research [9, 124–128].

Several chemical methods have been developed in recent years to synthesize monodispersed colloids of ferromagnetic nanoparticles [129–143]. While these techniques work well for simple elemental and oxide based ferromagnets, there are difficulties in producing alloy nanoparticles through the chemical route as the process involves toxic and often inflammable metallorganics combined with difficulties in stoichiometry control. The magnetic alloys of particular interest in nanoparticle

form are the ordered and disordered phases of CoPt and FePt. The large magnetocrystalline anisotropy of these alloys, combined with their chemical stability and corrosion resistance make them attractive for ultra high density recording media.

In this chapter we describe the use of Pulsed Laser Ablation in Aqueous Medium (PLAAM) [144] to synthesize CoPt alloy nanoparticles. Here we report the magnetization dynamics of the nanoparticles of the disordered low temperature fcc phase of $\text{Co}_{0.5}\text{Pt}_{0.5}$ alloy. Our analysis of the magnetization and demagnetization dynamics of these nanoparticles indicates two distinct particle size distributions. This conclusion is in agreement with the results of Transmission Electron Microscopy measurements.

3.2 Sample fabrication

Preparation of CoPt colloids using PLAAM technique has been described in the experimental chapter. The morphology and composition of the CoPt nanoparticles were characterized using Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) and Energy Dispersive X-ray (EDX) spectroscopy respectively. Samples for these measurements were prepared by drying a drop of the colloidal solution on a suitable template. Commercial carbon coated Cu grids and highly ordered pyrolytic graphite (HOPG) plates have been used as templates for TEM and EDX measurements, respectively. Solid samples for magnetization measurements were prepared by adding a low melting point (~ 330 K) water soluble analytical grade polymer (polyethylene glycol) to the colloid and dried completely through vacuum evaporation. This process also minimizes interparticle magnetic interactions and help in the formation of micelles by shielding the repulsion between the ionic heads of the surfactant [145, 146].

3.3 Results and discussion

Fig. 3.1 shows a transmission electron micrograph of the nanophase $\text{Co}_{0.5}\text{Pt}_{0.5}$ alloy dispersed on a carbon coated Cu grid. As evident from the micrograph, the

Fig. 3.1: *Transmission Electron Microscope image of the sodium dodecylsulfate (SDS) coated CoPt nanoparticles.*

nanoparticles have a droplet type of morphology and their size varies from ~ 1.5 nm to ~ 6 nm. A careful examination of the morphology of larger droplets indicates agglomeration of much smaller particles. Energy dispersive X-ray microanalysis of the colloidal solution of CoPt dispersed on HOPG plate showed the presence of Co and Pt in the sample. A point to point EDX analysis also revealed a constant Co/Pt ratio. While a quantitative compositional analysis with EDX is difficult, the uniformity of composition and the fact that the original stoichiometry of the target is maintained in Pulsed Laser Ablation, suggest that the Co and Pt are present in equiatomic composition. Scanning Electron Microscopy of the graphite surface also revealed agglomeration/accumulation of CoPt nanoparticles at the step edges of the HOPG single crystal substrate.

We now focus on the magnetic response of SDS-encapsulated CoPt alloy nanoparticles dispersed in the polymeric matrix. In order to check the contribution of the surfactant polymer matrix to the total magnetization, CoPt-free samples of SDS-

PEG were measured. The response of this matrix is predominantly diamagnetic which becomes significant only at fields in excess of $\simeq 5$ kOe. The field-cooled (FC) and zero-field-cooled (ZFC) magnetization measured at 500 Oe as a function of temperature is shown in Fig. 3.2. These low-field ZFC and FC curves, which first bifurcate at $T \leq 260$ K remain separated down to $\simeq 10$ K where the moment shows a rapid increase on lowering the temperature. A magnified view of low-field ZFC and FC curves in the temperature window of 250 K to 275 K is shown in the inset ‘a’ for clarity. The value of the FC and ZFC moment remains the same over a narrow interval of temperature, and then the ZFC moment shows a sharp drop below 4 K. Measurements of magnetization as a function of field below 2 K also show a distinct hysteresis (inset ‘b’ of Fig. 3.2). The separation of the zero-field-cooled and field-cooled branches of magnetization curves on decreasing the temperature is a characteristic feature of an agglomeration of superparamagnetic particles. At low temperature, the characteristic time scale of thermal fluctuations of the particle moment about the magnetic easy axis drops below the time scale of measurement, causing a drop in moment. The temperature (T_b) at which blocking of the moment occurs for a given applied field is expressed as [147],

$$T_b(H) = \frac{K_u V}{k_\beta \ln(\tau_m/\tau_o)} \left(1 - \frac{H}{H_k}\right)^2, \quad (3.1)$$

where τ_m is the measurement time, typically chosen to be 100 seconds for a dc measurement, k_β the Boltzmann constant, τ_o ($\sim 10^{-9}$ sec) the characteristic relaxation time, V the particle volume, K_u the uniaxial anisotropy constant and H_k the anisotropy field which is given in terms of saturation magnetization M_s as $H_k = 2K_u/M_s$. The magnetic moment under ZFC and FC conditions of an aggregate of

Fig. 3.2: Temperature dependence of the zero-field-cooled (solid circles) and field-cooled (open circles) magnetization of the CoPt nanoparticles dispersed in a polymer matrix measured at 500 Oe. Magnified view in the temperature window of 250 K to 275 K is shown in the inset (a). Inset (b) shows the hysteretic behavior of magnetization vs. field at 2 K.

superparamagnetic particles at $T > T_b$ is expressed as,

$$M_{ZFC}^{sp} = M_{FC}^{sp} = M_s L \left(\frac{M_s V H}{k_\beta T} \right), \quad (3.2)$$

where L is the Langevin function. The magnetization below the blocking temperature on the other hand, depends on the magnetic history of the sample, which leads to a hysteresis in M vs H measurements. This is seen in the inset of Fig. 3.2. The zero-field-cooled and field-cooled magnetization in this case are given by [8],

$$M_{ZFC}^{bl} = \frac{M_s^2 H}{3K_u}, \quad (3.3)$$

Fig. 3.3: Zero-field-cooled magnetization isotherms of the CoPt nanoparticles measured at 10 K, 30 K, 50 K, 70 K, 90 K, 110 K, 130 K, 150 K, 200 K and 250 K. Raw data without background subtraction are shown in the inset (a). Inset (b) of the figure shows the dependence of magnetization on H/T .

and

$$M_{FC}^{bl} = M_s L \left(\frac{M_s V H}{k_\beta T_b} \right), \quad (3.4)$$

respectively where the superscript ‘bl’ denotes the blocked regime.

As evident from Eq. 3.2, the magnetization in the superparamagnetic regime ($T > T_b$) must scale with H/T . In order to establish this dependence, we have measured zero-field-cooled magnetization isotherms at several temperatures. The background corrected data are shown in Fig. 3.3 along with the dependence of magnetization on H/T , whereas the raw data are shown in the inset ‘a’ of Fig. 3.3. The diamagnetic background contribution of the polymer-surfactant matrix has been subtracted from the original data to obtain these curves. No tendency of saturation was observed even upto a field of 45 kOe, as expected for an assembly of SPM particles. Interestingly, we notice a rather sharp bend in the magnetization

curves separating the high-field and the low-field regions at ~ 1 kOe. The scaling of all the isothermal magnetization curves onto a single line, as seen in the inset of Fig. 3.3 is consistent with the behavior of a superparamagnetic (SPM) system. However, a simple Langevin function

$$M\left(\frac{H}{T}\right) = \varepsilon M_s L\left(\frac{M_s V H}{k_\beta T}\right), \quad (3.5)$$

where M_s is taken to be ~ 800 emu/cm³, *did not* converge to the experimental data for any plausible value of the parameters V (volume of a particle) and ε (total number of particle contained in the matrix). Since a system of fine particles invariably contains a distribution of sizes, which gives rise to a distribution of blocking temperatures, we next try to analyze our experimental results by introducing a log-normal type particle size distribution. The total magnetization in this case is given as [148],

$$M_{ZFC} = \varepsilon \int_0^{V_m(T)} M_{ZFC}^{sp} f(V) dV + \varepsilon \int_{V_m(T)}^{\infty} M_{ZFC}^{bl} f(V) dV, \quad (3.6)$$

and

$$M_{FC} = \varepsilon \int_0^{V_m(T)} M_{FC}^{sp} f(V) dV + \varepsilon \int_{V_m(T)}^{\infty} M_{FC}^{bl} f(V) dV, \quad (3.7)$$

where

$$V_m(T) = \frac{k_\beta T \ln(\tau_m/\tau_o)}{K_u (1 - H/H_k)^2}. \quad (3.8)$$

The solid and the dashed lines in the main panel of Fig. 3.4 show the simulated

Fig. 3.4: The ZFC and FC magnetization data of Fig 3.2 are reproduced here. The solid line and dashed line present simulated FC and ZFC curves respectively using single log-normal distribution. Inset (a) shows the nature of the distribution function used for simulation. $f_N(\sigma, d)$ stands for normalized log-normal distribution multiplied by weight factor. While open circles show the magnetization versus field divided by temperature at 200 K in frame (b), solid line presents a simulation curve.

temperature dependence of magnetization under zero-field-cooled and field-cooled conditions respectively using Eqs. (3.6), (3.7) and (3.8). The single log-normal distribution function used in this case $f(V) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}V\sigma} \exp\left[-\frac{[\ln(V)-\ln(V_z)]^2}{2\sigma^2}\right]$, is plotted in the inset 'a' of Fig. 3.4. The inadequacy of a single log-normal distribution is also apparent in Fig. 3.4 and also in the inset 'b' of Fig. 3.4, where the calculated magnetization M is plotted (solid line) as a function of H/T following,

$$M\left(\frac{H}{T}\right) = \varepsilon \int_0^\infty M_s f(V) L\left(\frac{M_s V H}{k_\beta T}\right) dV \quad (3.9)$$

along with the measured M at 200 K.

Since our TEM measurements indicate particles of two distinctly different sizes

and also the double bifurcation of M vs T curve seen in Fig. 3.2 suggest two blocking temperatures, a more precise analysis of the data can be performed by considering two log-normal distributions centered at the average particle diameters of 1.3 nm and 5.9 nm as deduced from the TEM. In this case ZFC and FC can be written as,

$$M_{ZFC} = \sum_{i=1,2} \left[\varepsilon_i \int_0^{V_{mi}(T)} M_{ZFC_i}^{sp} f_i(V) dV + \varepsilon_i \int_{V_{mi}(T)}^{\infty} M_{ZFC_i}^{bl} f_i(V) dV \right] \quad (3.10)$$

and

$$M_{FC} = \sum_{i=1,2} \left[\varepsilon_i \int_0^{V_{mi}(T)} M_{FC_i}^{sp} f_i(V) dV + \varepsilon_i \int_{V_{mi}(T)}^{\infty} M_{FC_i}^{bl} f_i(V) dV \right] \quad (3.11)$$

The calculated curves based on these equations are plotted in Fig. 3.5 along with the measured data. Clearly, this construction matches better with the experimental data than the single log-normal distribution. The same parameters also reproduce the M vs H/T plot following the equation;

$$M \left(\frac{H}{T} \right) = \sum_{i=1,2} \varepsilon_i \int_0^{\infty} M_s f_i(V) L \left(\frac{M_s V H}{k_{\beta} T} \right) dV \quad (3.12)$$

as shown by the solid line in inset 'b' of Fig. 3.5. The individual contributions of the smaller and the bigger particles to magnetization are also plotted in the same inset as dotted and dashed lines, respectively. It is interesting to note that the magnetic moment corresponding to the bigger particles become almost constant above ~ 1 kOe after the initial sharp rise. The high-field behavior of the magnetization at a fixed temperature can, thus, be explained as a normal superparamagnetic response of the smaller particles centered around ~ 1.3 nm diameter. The anisotropy energy

Fig. 3.5: The solid line and dashed line present simulated FC and ZFC curves respectively using double log-normal distribution. Inset (a) shows the nature of the distribution functions used for simulation. Open circles shows the magnetization versus field divided by temperature at 200 K in frame (b), While the solid line in the inset (b) presents simulated magnetization, dashed line and dotted line show the contribution to magnetization from the bigger and smaller particles respectively. The relevant parameters used in simulation are discussed in the text.

derived from the calculations comes out to be $\sim 0.94 \times 10^6$ J/m³ and $\sim 0.1 \times 10^6$ J/m³ for the smaller (~ 1.3 nm) and larger (~ 5.9 nm) particles, respectively.

Interestingly, even the dual log-normal distribution seems to be insufficient to explain the magnetization over the entire range of temperature. The important parameter that is normally overlooked in such analysis is the variation of anisotropy energy with particle size. Usually, a single anisotropy energy corresponding to the mean of particle size distribution is used. However, it has been observed that anisotropy energy is a sensitive function of the particle size. For example, a variation of particle diameter from 1.5 nm to 1.9 nm in an ultrafine cobalt nanoparticle system, results in a change in K_u from 0.83×10^6 to 0.73×10^6 J/m³ [139]. This issue is usually left unaddressed in the literature. However, in the present case the effect is noticeable due to the broad and peculiar size distribution. Both the log-normal particle dis-

Fig. 3.6: Open circles show the result of magnetic relaxation measurement at 2 K on a sample after cooling it to 2 K in the presence of 20 kOe field. The inadequacy in fitting the experimental data with single exponential decay (solid line) is clear from the figure. Solid circles show the magnetic relaxation at 10 K under the same field cooled condition. Inset of the figure shows temperature dependence of the zero-field-cooled (solid squares) and field-cooled (open squares) magnetization of the CoPt nanoparticles measured at 20 kOe.

tributions with their respective weight factors as a function of particle diameter are plotted in the inset ‘a’ of Fig. 3.5. As evident from this figure, there is an overlap of the two distributions over a considerable range of size. Therefore, the use of a single anisotropy energy corresponding to each distribution function is certainly insufficient. A realistic simulation of the magnetization should also incorporate the variation of K_u with particle size, which is computationally intensive. Here we would also like to point out that the microstructure of the bigger particle needs to be examined with high resolution electron microscopy. Some of the larger particles may actually be an agglomeration of smaller particles. In such situation, interparticle interactions can increase the blocking temperature [149].

A further verification of the size distribution comes from the magnetization relaxation measurements on our nanoparticles. Since the relaxation rate of magnetic

moment in nanoparticles is a sharp function of the particle size, distribution of the latter in our case is expected to manifest itself in the characteristic relaxation time. In our case, the relaxation measurement was performed by cooling the sample down to the measurement temperature in 20 kOe applied field. Once the temperature is stabilized, the field was reduced to zero in ‘no overshoot’ mode in 300 seconds. After a waiting time of 100 seconds, the remanent magnetization was measured as a function of time. In Fig. 3.6 we have shown the decay of magnetic moment with time for CoPt alloy nanoparticles cooled in an applied field of 20 kOe to the measurement temperature of 2 K. The field-cooled (FC) and zero-field-cooled (ZFC) magnetization measured at 20 kOe as a function of temperature is shown in the inset. As can be seen in Fig. 3.6 and in the inset of Fig. 3.6, there is an order of magnitude drop in magnetic moment when the first data point of the magnetic relaxation has been taken. This is basically due to the relaxation of smaller particles. Therefore, the relaxation data presented in the figure reflect only the distribution of characteristics relaxation time for bigger particles with certain size distribution. A fit to the relaxation data using the simple first order exponential decay function is shown as solid line in Fig. 3.6. Clearly, this dependence does not explain the relaxation adequately. The inexplicability of this fitting is due to the presence of particle size distribution in our sample as stated before. At 10 K, the nanoparticles were found to relax almost instantly on removal of the field. The magnetization, therefore appears to remain constant during the accessible time of measurement. This is typical of a paramagnetic system or a SPM system above T_c , where the particles react immediately to a field change. At 2 K, however, most of the particles are blocked and a typical activated relaxation is observed which follows the Arrhenius law.

In order to ascertain the magnitude of anisotropy in this system, we have recorded the temperature dependent magnetization at a higher field (20 kOe). If the energy

associated with the applied field exceeds the anisotropy energy, then one would expect a overlapping set of ZFC and FC curves, since at all temperatures the preferential magnetization orientation of the nanoparticles will be essentially the direction of the field. Only a weak paramagnetic response is expected as a function of temperature, reminiscent of the thermal fluctuation of individual moments about the direction of applied field. The result of this high-field measurement is shown in the inset of Fig. 3.6. As expected, we find no separation between the ZFC and FC curves within the experimental limits.

3.4 Conclusions

Cobalt platinum nanoparticles dispersed in surfactant polymer matrix were synthesized using Pulsed Laser Ablation of a composite alloy target in an aqueous medium. For CoPt nanoparticles prepared using this technique the zero-field-cooled and field-cooled magnetization measurements at low-fields reveal two distinct temperatures (260 K and 4 K) where the ZFC and FC curves bifurcate from each other, corresponding to the characteristic blocking of an aggregate of superparamagnetic particles. Magnetization vs. field measurements at different temperatures show strong evidence of superparamagnetic nature of the particles. The low coercive field (~ 400 Oe) of this assembly at 2K is essentially a characteristics of low temperature fcc phase of $\text{Co}_{0.5}\text{Pt}_{0.5}$ nanoparticles. Magnetization measurements suggest a distribution of two different particle sizes centered at ~ 1.3 nm and ~ 5.9 nm, which is consistent with Electron Microscopy observations. The magnetic anisotropy energy of these particles is 0.9×10^6 J/m³ and 0.1×10^6 J/m³ respectively.

4. MORPHOLOGICAL, CRYSTALLOGRAPHIC AND MAGNETIC CHARACTERISTICS OF CoPt FILMS

4.1 Introduction

Studies of the correlation between crystallographic as well as morphological structure and magnetic coercivity of CoPt and FePt alloy films have been a topic of considerable interest in recent years due to the strong perpendicular magnetic anisotropy and chemical inertness of these alloys, which make them suitable for high density recording applications [30, 33, 39, 40, 150–168]. The key structural feature responsible for magnetic anisotropy of these systems is the ordering of Pt and Co or Fe atoms in the crystal lattice. The ordered $L1_0$ phase at equiatomic composition comprises of alternate sequence of Co (Fe) and Pt planes along the crystallographic c -axis [169]. Studies of coercivity and magnetization reversal in granular thin films of CoPt and FePt are of interest as well. When the size of grains becomes small enough to make them mono-domain, the magnetic response of the system may differ significantly from that in the bulk form.

The experimental conditions that drive a particular growth mechanism of CoPt (FePt) films and the linkage between crystallographic and morphological structure, vis-a-vis magnetocrystalline anisotropy, saturation and remanent magnetization, coercive field and magnetic domain structure need to be studied for each process of

growth. Most of the earlier research on thin films of CoPt employed sputtering [39, 150–154] or molecular beam epitaxy (MBE) [155, 156] to grow textured and epitaxial films. Majority of these works have been carried out on (001) MgO substrates. The lattice parameter of MgO (cubic, $a = 4.21 \text{ \AA}$) is larger by 8.5 and 9.6 % compared to the basal plane unit cell parameter of $L1_0$ FePt and CoPt respectively. The large lattice mismatch invariably affects epitaxial growth and magnetic properties of the films, whose extent needs to be quantified by depositing films on single crystal substrates which provide different degree of lattice mismatch.

In this chapter we report PLD growth of epitaxial CoPt films on (001) cut LaAlO_3 (LAO), SrTiO_3 (STO) and MgO single crystals with the objectives to (i) demonstrate the feasibility of growth of stoichiometric films from ablation of an alloy target, (ii) vary the extent of substrate induced strain by depositing films on single crystal substrates of different lattice parameter such that effects of both tensile as well compressive strain on growth morphology are addressed, (iii) establish correlations between film morphology, phase purity and magnetic properties, (iv) determine minimum growth temperature to stabilize the high coercive tetragonal phase, and (v) address the role of kinetic conditions, such as deposition rate, in stabilizing a particular growth morphology at several growth temperatures. We note that the surface morphology of these films depends strongly on deposition temperature (T_d) and growth rate (G_r), in addition to the lattice mismatch with the substrate, which can be characterized in terms of the strain parameter ϵ defined as $\epsilon = \frac{a_{\text{bulk}} - a_{\text{substrate}}}{a_{\text{bulk}}} \times 100$, where a is the lattice parameter. Values of the parameter ϵ for in-plane and out-of-plane c -axis growth of the $L1_0$ phase, and for the fcc phase on three different substrates used in this study are listed in Tab. 4.1. For MgO (001) [$a = 4.21 \text{ \AA}$], the ϵ for out-of-plane and in-plane c -axis growth of the $L1_0$ phase is - 10.7 % and - 13.8 % respectively. The films on STO (001) [$a = 3.905 \text{ \AA}$] also experience tensile strain in both orientations but it is nominal ($\epsilon = - 2.7 \%$ for

substrate	crystallographic structure	growth direction	ϵ
LAO (001)	fcc	–	- 0.5 %
LAO (001)	L1 ₀	in-plane c-axis	- 2.5 %
LAO (001)	L1 ₀	out-of-plane c-axis	+ 0.3 %
MgO (001)	fcc	–	- 11.6 %
MgO (001)	L1 ₀	in-plane c-axis	- 13.8 %
MgO (001)	L1 ₀	out-of-plane c-axis	- 10.7 %
STO (001)	fcc	–	- 3.5 %
STO (001)	L1 ₀	in-plane c-axis	- 5.5 %
STO (001)	L1 ₀	out-of-plane c-axis	- 2.7 %

Tab. 4.1: Variation of strain parameter ϵ due to mismatch in lattice parameter on various substrates. The lattice parameter of LAO (001), MgO (001) and STO (001) substrates are 3.792 Å, 4.21 Å and 3.905 Å respectively. While CoPt in fcc phase has a cubic lattice parameter of 3.772 Å, the lattice parameters of L1₀ CoPt in the bulk form are $a = b = 3.803$ Å and $c = 3.701$ Å.

out-of-plane and - 5.5 % for in-plane c-axis growth) as compared to that on MgO (001). The (001) face of LAO [cubic, $a = 3.792$ Å], however provides an ideal square planar lattice with minimum lattice mismatch for epitaxial growth of the L1₀ phase of CoPt in either orientation (- 2.5 and 0.3 % for in-plane and out-of-plane c-axis growth respectively). The choice of different ϵ allows tuning of the strain and hence the surface morphology of the films, provided the flux of adatoms on the substrate is kept low. At high flux densities, kinetic considerations eliminate the morphological features evolved due to an imbalance of strain and interfacial energies of the film. The best c-axis oriented epitaxial L1₀ CoPt thin films display a coercive field ($H_{c\perp}$) as high as ≈ 30 kOe and anisotropy energy density of $\sim 4.62 \times 10^6$ J/m³ at ambient temperature.

4.2 Deposition of thin films

Three series of cobalt-platinum samples of equiatomic composition have been prepared under different growth conditions as listed in Tab. 4.2, to evaluate their effect on morphology, crystallographic structure and magnetic properties of the films. The

series	G_r ($\approx \text{\AA}/\text{sec}$)	t_F (nm)	T_d ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	substrate	post annealing time (minutes)	$H_{c\parallel}/H_{c\perp}$ (kOe)
A	1	100	600	STO	No	0.074/-
	1	100	700	STO	No	4.2/-
	1	100	800	STO	No	6/-
	1	100	700	STO	30	5.9/-
B	1	20	700	STO	30	-/-
	1	30	700	STO	30	6.4/6.7
	1	50	700	STO	30	6.2/5.1
	1	100	700	STO	30	5.4/4.3
	1	20	700	MgO	30	-/-
	1	30	700	MgO	30	8.3/-
	1	50	700	MgO	30	7.9/-
	1	100	700	MgO	30	6.8/-
C	0.4	50	700	LAO	25	-/-
	0.4	50	750	LAO	25	-/-
	0.4	50	800	LAO	25	-/-
	0.4	50	700	MgO	25	-/-
	0.4	50	750	MgO	25	-/-
	0.4	50	800	MgO	25	-/-
	0.4	50	700	STO	25	-/7
	0.4	50	750	STO	25	-/16
	0.4	50	800	STO	25	0.4/37

Tab. 4.2: *Sample preparation conditions in the different series. The table also lists the in-plane and out-of-plane coercive field.*

purpose of preparing each series is as follows; In series ‘A’ samples of thickness (t_F) ≈ 100 nm grown on (001) STO at 600, 700 and 800 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, the effects of deposition temperature (T_d) and post deposition annealing were studied. Series ‘B’ films were prepared to study the effects of film thickness. This series consists of four films of thickness ranging from 20 to 100 nm grown at 700 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ on STO and MgO substrates followed by annealing for 30 minutes at the growth temperature. The growth rate (G_r) for these two sets of samples was $\approx 1 \text{\AA}/\text{sec}$. The last series, series ‘C’, was prepared at a slower growth rate ($\approx 0.4 \text{\AA}/\text{sec}$). It consists of three set of samples deposited at 700, 750 and 800 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ on LAO, STO and MgO mounted side-by-side on the substrate heater. The thickness of these films was $\simeq 50$ nm. All thicknesses

mentioned above were measured with a stylus based surface profilometer.

4.2.1 Effects of growth temperature and post growth annealing

In Fig. 4.1(a) we show XRD profiles of the series ‘A’ samples (deposited on STO at 600, 700 and 800 °C) together with the diffraction profile of a bare substrate. The pattern for the sample deposited at 600 °C shows only one peak at $2\theta = 48.12^\circ$, which can be attributed to the (200) reflection of the disordered A1 (fcc) phase. This reflection developed into a doublet on increasing the T_d to 700 °C, and finally goes back to a single peak shifted to higher 2θ at $T_d = 800$ °C. The doublet seen here is due to the mixing of the (200) and (002) reflections of the L1₀ phase with some c-axis grains oriented parallel and others oriented perpendicular to the film plane. At the highest deposition temperature, i.e., 800 °C, although the (002) peak of the L1₀ phase becomes prominent, a discernible shoulder remains on its low angle side. A marked increase in the intensity and sharpness of (001), (002) and (003) peaks of this film indicates significant improvement in the degree of chemical ordering at the elevated T_d .

Fig. 4.1(b) presents the in-plane magnetization ($M-H_{\parallel}$) from $+H_{max}$ to $-H_{max}$ of the films whose X-ray diffraction data are shown in Fig. 4.1(a). Only half loops were taken to save the SQUID time. Since there are three ordered variants of CoPt which may co-exist in the film, each with c-axis parallel to one of the cube edge directions i.e., [001], [010] and [100] of the substrate [see, inset Fig. 4.1(b)], the external field was applied parallel to the film plane at 45° with respect to the [100] and [010] direction of the substrate as shown in the lower inset of Fig. 4.1(b). The coercive field ($H_{c\parallel}$) deduced from these measurements is 104 Oe, 6 kOe and 8.4 kOe for the films deposited at 600, 700 and 800 °C respectively. Since the field for $H_{c\parallel}$ measurement was applied diagonally, the true value of $H_{c\parallel}$ would be the component of measured $H_{c\parallel}$ along the [100] or [010] direction. The correct $H_{c\parallel}$ deduced in this

Fig. 4.1: (a) X-ray diffraction profiles of 100 nm CoPt thin films deposited at various substrate temperatures on single crystal (001) cut STO. Samples were cooled down to room temperature immediately after the deposition. The diffraction profile of single crystal STO (001) is also shown at the bottom panel. Arrows at the top panel indicate the positions of fundamental as well as superlattice reflections of $L1_0$ ordered phase. (b) In-plane magnetization loops of the same samples. A schematic sketch of the direction of $H_{||}$ is presented in the lower inset of the figure. The upper inset represents a schematic of the three c -axis variants of the $L1_0$ phase.

manner then become 74 Oe, 4.2 kOe and 5.9 kOe for 600, 700 and 800 °C films respectively. Since all measurements of magnetization in parallel configuration were performed with field applied along [110], we will only refer to corrected value of $H_{c||}$ unless otherwise specified. It is important to mention here that all magnetization data were corrected for the contribution of the substrate. The absolute value of

moment has an error of $\pm 15\%$ due to the uncertainty in the measurement of sample volume.

The extremely low coercivity ($H_{c\parallel} \approx 74$ Oe) of the film deposited at 600°C is consistent with our X-ray data which shows only the disordered A1 phase at this T_d . Such a low coercivity has been reported by several workers [33, 40, 156, 157] in their A1 phase CoPt films. For the film deposited at 700°C , the $H_{c\parallel}$ increases to 4.2 kOe. This increase in $H_{c\parallel}$ is consistent with X-ray diffraction results which show the formation of the $L1_0$ phase with grains of c-axis in the plane of the substrate as well as perpendicular to it. Samples prepared at 800°C display even higher $H_{c\parallel}$ (≈ 5.9 kOe). Crystallographically, such films are pure $L1_0$ phase with c-axis normal to the plane of the substrate.

There are three important features in the M - H_{\parallel} data of Fig. 4.1(b) which need to be highlighted; (i) while the magnetization of the 600°C film saturates at very low field (≈ 5 kOe), the film of $T_d = 700$ and 800°C show a non-saturating tendency of magnetization even at the maximum applied field of ≈ 20 kOe, (ii) the total magnetic moment of the films goes down with the increasing deposition temperature, and (iii), the coercivity increases non-monotonically as the T_d increases from 600 to 800°C . Since $L1_0$ CoPt system exhibits very high anisotropy field H_k (≈ 123 kOe) [159] with c-axis as the easy-axis of magnetization, the volume fraction of the film whose c-axis lies perpendicular to the surface of the substrate would behave more like a paramagnet for an in-plane measuring field. This would lead to a non-saturating M - H curve. While the first two observations made on the magnetization data of Fig. 4.1(b) indicate that crystallographic domains of $L1_0$ phase with c-axis in the plane of the substrate exist in 700 and 800°C films, their fraction decreases in 800°C films as suggested by the low remanence and large coercivity of such films. The 600°C film on the other hand is single-phase disordered fcc with its characteristically small H_c .

Fig. 4.2: (a) X-ray diffraction profiles of as deposited and post annealed 100 nm CoPt thin films grown at 700°C at a growth rate of $\approx 1 \text{ \AA}/\text{sec}$ on STO (001). The diffraction profile of single crystal STO (001) is also shown at the bottom panel. Arrows at the top panel indicate the positions of fundamental as well as superlattice reflections of $L1_0$ ordered phase. Dotted line in the figure marks the position of (200) reflection. (b) In-plane magnetization loops of the same samples.

Fig. 4.2 shows the effects of thermal annealing on crystal structure and magnetization of a film deposited at 700°C on STO. The broad peak centered at $2\theta \approx 48^\circ$ in the XRD profile of the unannealed film splits into two peaks corresponding to the (200) and (002) reflections of the $L1_0$ phase on the heat treatment. This change is accompanied by enhancement of the intensity under the (001) and (003) reflections, indicating a better chemical ordering with c-axis of the ordered phase

Fig. 4.3: (a) X-ray diffraction profiles of CoPt thin films of various thicknesses deposited at 700°C on STO (001) at a growth rate of $\approx 1 \text{ \AA}/\text{sec}$. All the samples were post annealed for 30 minutes. The diffraction profile of single crystal STO (001) is also shown at the bottom panel. Arrows at the top panel indicate the positions of fundamental as well as superlattice reflections of $L1_0$ ordered phase. Dotted line in the figure marks the position of (200) reflection. (b) In-plane magnetization loops of the same samples. Magnetization data have been presented with 15 % error bars. (c) - (e) SEM micrographs of the samples of different thicknesses.

aligned parallel to the film normal. The observed increase in coercivity from 4.2 kOe to 5.9 kOe is consistent with the results of structural analysis.

4.2.2 Effect of film thickness (t_F) and epitaxial strain

Fig. 4.3(a) shows a series of XRD patterns for films (series B) of various thicknesses ranging from 30 to 100 nm grown on STO at 700°C and annealed at the same temperature for 30 minutes. The fundamental and superlattice peaks of the $L1_0$ phase are observed clearly in all the samples. The M-H curves for in-plane magnetization $M(H_{\parallel})$ and the morphology of these films are also shown in Fig. 4.3(b) and Fig. 4.3(c, d, e) respectively. We observe an interconnected maze-like pattern of CoPt layer in the 20 nm thick film. On increase in thickness to 30 nm, the void fraction

Fig. 4.4: a) X-ray diffraction profiles of CoPt thin films of various thicknesses deposited at 700°C on MgO (001) at a growth rate of $\approx 1 \text{ \AA}/\text{sec}$. All the samples were post annealed for 30 minutes. The diffraction profile of single crystal MgO (001) is also shown at the bottom panel. Arrows at the top panel indicate the positions of fundamental as well as superlattice reflections of $L1_0$ ordered phase. Dotted line in the figure marks the position of (200) reflection. (b) In-plane magnetization loops of the same samples. Magnetization data have been presented with 15 % error bars. (c) - (e) SEM micrographs of the samples of different thicknesses.

in the film decreases, and at $t_F = 50 \text{ nm}$, the percolating network expands at the expense of voids and the film becomes almost continuous.

A set of samples was also prepared on MgO substrates, loaded side-by-side to STO whose results have been discussed in the preceding section. The XRD profiles, $M-H_{\parallel}$ curves and surface morphology of these samples are presented in Fig. 4.4. Interestingly, the morphological features of these films are similar to those deposited on STO [Fig. 4.2] in spite of a large difference in strain parameters ϵ_{MgO} and ϵ_{STO} . It appears that the higher G_r ($\approx 1 \text{ \AA}/\text{sec}$) used here and the moderate growth temperature ($\sim 700^{\circ}\text{C}$), conspire to increase the supersaturation of adatoms on surface which reduces the critical size of a cluster beyond which it does not grow,

and increase the cluster nucleation rate [87, 170]. These two factors appear to suppress the effect of strain leading to a similar morphology of the films deposited on STO and MgO.

Fig. 4.5: Variation of in-plane coercive field $H_{c||}$ with thickness for the films on STO (001) and MgO (001) single crystal deposited at 700 °C at a growth rate of $\approx 1 \text{ \AA}/\text{sec}$. Inset shows the dependence of I_{200}/I_{002} on film thickness. All the samples were post annealed for 30 minutes. Solid lines in the figure are guide to the eye.

We note in Fig. 4.3(a) that with increasing thickness, the intensity of (200) reflection of the $L1_0$ increases and for 100 nm thick film it becomes equal to the intensity of the (002) peak. Fig. 4.4(a) shows the XRD profiles of the 30, 50 and 100 nm thick films grown on MgO. These results reveal that unlike the films on STO, MgO favors a growth with c-axis of the $L1_0$ phase in the plane of the substrate. Here the intensity of the (200) peak (I_{200}) increases faster than that of the (002) peak (I_{002}). In the inset of Fig. 4.5 we plot the variation of I_{200}/I_{002} for the films deposited on MgO and STO as a function of their thickness. It is expected that the increased fraction of the c-axis in-plane phase on MgO with increasing t_F should lead to a distinct increase in low-field magnetization for in-plane measurements. Our data for $M(H_{||})$ (Fig. 4.4(b)) however, do not reveal a clear trend with t_F within the accuracy ($\pm 15 \%$) of these measurements. The in-plane coercivity ($H_{c||}$) of these

films as a function of their thickness is plotted in Fig. 4.5. A marginal enhancement in coercivity is seen as the films are made thinner. By comparing this result with the microstructure of the films, it becomes clear that a percolative network is more coercive than a continuous film.

Fig. 4.6: Perpendicular and in-plane magnetization loops for the films of thickness (a) 100 nm (b) 50 nm and (c) 30 nm deposited at 700°C on STO (001) at a growth rate of $\approx 1 \text{ \AA}/\text{sec}$. All the samples were post annealed for 30 minutes.

In order to understand the magnetization reversal process in films of ordered $L1_0$ phase with mixed crystallographic domains, some with their c -axis parallel and some perpendicular to the substrate plane, we have measured the magnetization of the series ‘B’ samples [$T_d = 700$ °C] grown on STO in H_{\parallel} and H_{\perp} geometries. The results of these measurements are shown in Fig. 4.6. The magnetic field for the in-plane (H_{\parallel}) measurements was applied at 45° with respect to the [100] and [010] direction of the substrate as mentioned in the previous section. The component of $H_{c\parallel}$ along [100] or [010] direction is expected to be equal to $H_{c\perp}$ if the three variants of c -axis are present with equal abundance. Interestingly, the calculated values of the $H_{c\parallel}$ along [100] and [010] (listed in Tab. 4.2) match reasonably well with the measured values of $H_{c\perp}$ irrespective of the film thickness.

4.2.3 Fractals and nanodots at low growth rate

The evolution of film morphology with deposition temperature and growth rate is intimately linked with the epitaxial strain parameter ϵ provided the rate of growth is not large [151, 163]. In order to study the strain induced crystallographic and morphological changes, a set of samples (series ‘C’) was prepared using a slow deposition rate (≈ 0.4 Å/sec) on (001) LAO, (001) STO and (001) MgO.

In Fig. 4.7 and 4.8 respectively we show XRD patterns and SEM micrographs of the films grown on LAO and MgO. The XRD profiles of the films grown on STO are shown in Fig. 4.9(a). From the XRD data of Fig. 4.7(a), it is difficult to say whether there exist any c -axis variants in the film on LAO when grown at 700 °C because the position of the (200) reflection in $\theta - 2\theta$ scan merges with the (002) (using pseudocubic unit cell) reflection of the substrate. But there is a clear signature of this in films deposited on the other two substrates. It was also evident from the relative intensity of the (200) and (002) reflections [see Fig. 4.8(a) and 4.9(a)] that the fraction of the domains with in-plane c -axis is more in the film on MgO as

Fig. 4.7: (a) X-ray diffraction profiles of 50 nm CoPt thin films deposited at various substrate temperatures at a growth rate of $\approx 0.4 \text{ \AA}/\text{sec}$ on single crystal LAO (001). All the samples were post annealed for 25 minutes. The diffraction profile of single crystal LAO (001) is also shown at the bottom panel. Arrows at the top panel indicate the positions of fundamental as well as superlattice reflections of $L1_0$ ordered phase. (b) and (c) SEM images of the samples deposited at 700 and 800°C respectively.

Fig. 4.8: (a) X-ray diffraction profiles of 50 nm CoPt thin films deposited at various substrate temperatures at a growth rate of $\approx 0.4\text{ }\text{\AA}/\text{sec}$ on single crystal MgO (001). All the samples were post annealed for 25 minutes. The diffraction profile of single crystal MgO (001) is also shown at the bottom panel. Arrows at the top panel indicate the positions of fundamental as well as superlattice reflections of $L1_0$ ordered phase. Dotted line in the figure marks the position of (200) reflection. (b) SEM image of the sample deposited at $750\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

compared to that in the film on STO. The c-axis lattice parameter of these films calculated from the position of the (002) reflection shows a small but distinct drop at the higher growth temperatures [see Fig. 4.9(b)]. This change is independent of the substrate used. At the highest deposition temperature i.e., $800\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the c-axis lattice parameters for films on all the three substrates compare reasonably well with the bulk value of $3.701\text{ }\text{\AA}$.

Fig. 4.9: (a) X-ray diffraction profiles of 50 nm CoPt thin films deposited at various substrate temperatures at a growth rate of ≈ 0.4 Å/sec on single crystal STO (001). All the samples were post annealed for 25 minutes. The diffraction profile of single crystal STO (001) is also shown at the bottom panel. Arrows at the top panel indicate the positions of fundamental as well as superlattice reflections of $L1_0$ ordered phase. Dotted line in the figure marks the position of (200) reflection. (b) Change in c-axis lattice parameter for films on LAO, STO and MgO with deposition temperature. Solid lines are guide to the eye.

The SEM micrographs of the surface of these films present some interesting manifestations of epitaxial strain. As seen in Fig. 4.10(a) for film deposited on STO at 700 °C, the morphology is a self-similar fractal where the fractals do not form a percolating backbone over a length scale larger than $\simeq 5$ μm . On increasing the T_d to 750 °C, the maze-like structure breaks into islands. A similar morphology is seen

Fig. 4.10: SEM images and Perpendicular magnetization loops of 50 nm CoPt thin films deposited at various substrate temperatures at a growth rate of $\approx 0.4\text{ }\text{\AA}/\text{sec}$ on single crystal STO (001). All the samples were post annealed for 25 minutes. Magnetization panel for the sample grown $800\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ also shows data for in-plane configuration.

in films deposited on MgO at $750\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [see Fig. 4.8(b)]. Upon further increase of T_d to $800\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the islands on STO [Fig. 4.10(c)] acquire a smaller and nearly uniform size distribution ($\approx 200\text{ nm}$). The values of the thermal expansion coefficients of

STO and MgO ($11.1 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ and $12.8 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$, respectively [171]) are close to that of CoPt ($10.9 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ [172]). These data suggest that the ϵ parameter at T_d does not differ much from its room temperature value for MgO as well as STO. The breaking of the films can, therefore, be understood on the basis of the strain parameter calculated using room temperature lattice constants. The reason for these topological changes is suggested to depend on the imbalance of interfacial and strain energies that minimizes the contact area between film and the substrate with increasing T_d .

The most interesting case is when the films are grown on LAO which has nearly perfect lattice matching ($\epsilon = + 0.3 \%$) with the out-of-plane $L1_0$ CoPt at room temperature. As evident from Fig. 4.7(b) there is an irregular shaped island growth on LAO even at $700 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Since the coefficient of thermal expansion for LAO ($9.2 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$) is similar to that of CoPt [171], this breaking of the film can not be explained on the basis of strain alone. However, LAO undergoes a structural phase change from rhombohedral to cubic symmetry on heating above $600 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [173]. The lattice parameter and associated expansion coefficient of the cubic phase perhaps facilitate the island growth seen at $700 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The island morphology becomes sharper on increasing the T_d to $800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. This nanoscale structure that evolves at the higher T_d and low G_r is likely to be due to the enhanced desorption of adatoms from surface which leave large areas with little or no coverage. These regions can host new islands [174]. Similar observations have been made by Castaldi et al [161] for CoPt films deposited on oxidized Si substrates using electron beam evaporation technique.

4.2.4 Magnetic behavior of the fractals and nanodots grown on STO

We have addressed the magnetization and demagnetization characteristics of the films deposited at slow growth rate ($G_r \approx 0.4 \text{ \AA}/\text{sec}$) on STO (series ‘C’) in detail. The typical M-H loops at 300 K of the samples grown at 700, 750 and 800 °C are shown in Fig. 4.10 (d, e and f) respectively. These data are for applied field perpendicular to the plane of the film (H_{\perp}), except for 800 °C sample for which H_{\parallel} measurement is also shown. A striking feature of these data is a substantial increase in coercivity ($H_{c\perp}$) [see Tab. 4.2] with the increasing deposition temperatures. In order to understand the magnetization dynamics and its reversal mechanism let us consider the three samples separately.

Sample deposited at 700 °C does not show any saturation of the magnetic moment even at 30 kOe. The coercive field ($H_{c\perp}$), in this case is ≈ 7 kOe. We have already discussed the presence of c-axis variants of $L1_0$ phase with grains of c-axis parallel to [100] and [010] directions of the substrate for the sample deposited at 700 °C. Since c-axis is the easy-axis of magnetization in $L1_0$ phase of CoPt film, the fraction of $L1_0$ phase with in-plane c-axis play a major role in setting the magnetic response of the sample. The paramagnet-like contribution of the in-plane c-axis fraction of CoPt when the field is applied perpendicular to substrate surface would display a non-saturating tendency of magnetic moment even at very high field because of the large uniaxial anisotropy ($H_k \approx 123$ kOe) of $L1_0$ CoPt phase. The remanence squareness $S (= M_r/M_s)$, where M_s and M_r are the saturation and remanent magnetization respectively, of the series ‘C’ samples is plotted in the Fig. 4.11 as a function of T_d . The S parameter is $\simeq 0.85$ for the 700 °C deposited films. Although a high value of $S (> 0.5)$ has been attributed to exchange coupling amongst the particles [160], we believe that the large S seen in this sample of a fractal-like

Fig. 4.11: Variation of remanent ratio S and perpendicular coercive field $H_{c\perp}$ with deposition temperature for 50 nm CoPt thin films at a growth rate of $\approx 0.4 \text{ \AA}/\text{sec}$ on single crystal STO (001). All the samples were post annealed for 25 minutes.

morphology is a manifestation of pinning of the domain walls by the boundaries between adjacent c-axis variants where the easy axis changes by 90° [40].

For the sample deposited at 800°C the saturation field is beyond the maximum dc-field (46 kOe) used in these $M(H_\perp)$ measurements. This is indicated by the hysteresis loop shown in Fig. 4.10(f), which is neither symmetrical nor centered about the origin, and has no reversible region even at the maximum applied field. A very large $H_{c\perp}$ of ≈ 30 kOe is seen in these films. It is important to mention here that this $H_{c\perp}$ has been derived by taking the average of the magnetic field corresponding to zero moment from both sides of the hysteresis loop. The true $H_{c\perp}$ may be still higher because the loop did not reach saturation due to the limited value of the applied field [175]. Fig. 4.10(f) also shows the M-H curve taken in parallel field configuration. The uniaxial magnetic anisotropy K_u of this film, determined from the area enclosed by the parallel and perpendicular magnetization curves, comes out to be $\approx 4.62 \times 10^6 \text{ J/m}^3$, which is very close to the maximum value ($\sim 5.0 \times 10^6 \text{ J/m}^3$) reported in the literature [176].

Fig. 4.12: AFM and MFM images of 50 nm CoPt thin films deposited at (a) 750 °C and (b) 800 °C at a growth rate of $\approx 0.4 \text{ \AA}/\text{sec}$ on STO (001). Measurements were carried out on thermally demagnetized samples.

In order to establish a correlation between morphological features and magnetic domain structure of the films of the series ‘C’, we show in Fig. 4.12 the Atomic and Magnetic Force Micrographs taken from the same spot on the film. For the 750 °C sample, there is some discrepancy between the SEM image (Fig. 4.10 (b)) and the AFM image (Fig. 4.12 (a)). While the SEM image shows well-separated grains, the AFM image reveals a much smaller separation between them. The MFM image of this sample suggests that the magnetic domains are not confined to a physical grain, and also the boundary between two adjacent domains is not sharp. This clear non-conformity of the topographical structure and magnetic domain pattern suggest

that the grain boundaries do not play a significant role in pinning of domains and their reversal. The initial magnetization (M - H_{\perp}) loop of the sample with $T_d = 750$ °C shows a sharp rise with field and reaches 90 % of the saturation moment at $\simeq 3$ kOe, which is much lower than $H_{c\perp} \simeq 16$ kOe (Fig. 4.10(e)). Thus the MFM images clearly suggests that the domain walls in the film can easily propagate through the film surface without experiencing strong pinning at the grain boundaries [150].

The AFM image of the sample grown at $T_d = 800$ °C (Fig. 4.12(b)) is quite similar to its SEM image (Fig. 4.10(c)) which shows uniform and well-separated nanograins. The MFM image of individual grains does not show any domain boundaries. Since one can exactly map each feature of the AFM image onto the MFM image it is clear that each grain in the film is a single magnetic domain. The bright and dark features in the MFM image, which represent nanograins of reversed magnetization are similar in number, ensuring zero magnetization in the thermally demagnetized state. Another interesting aspect of this image is that the bright and dark features tend to group among themselves showing string-like structures and islands. Although the remanence squareness parameter S ($\simeq 0.59$) for this sample is close to that for a randomly oriented assembly of non-interacting Stoner-Wohlfarth (S-W) particles [22, 160], we cannot really rule out interaction between the particles. Further, a limited spatial resolution of MFM (≈ 50 nm) also makes it difficult to say whether the demagnetization process is via a coherent rotation of magnetization or due to a curling mode which can lead to vorticity in the spin system.

4.2.5 Relaxation of magnetization in single-domain nanodots

In order to understand the process of magnetization reversal, relaxation measurements of magnetization at constant negative bias field close to the coercive value ($H_{c\perp}$) were carried out on film deposited at 800 °C (series ‘C’). The theory of thermal fluctuations of the magnetic moment of single-domain ferromagnetic particles was

Fig. 4.13: Magnetic relaxation data as a function of various reverse magnetic fields. Solid lines are fit to the experimental data using the Néel-Brown formula (see text for details).

introduced by Néel [123] and further developed by Brown [177]. For the particles at zero applied field, the energy barrier between two equilibrium states of opposite moment is too high to observe magnetization reversal in a reasonable experimental time scale of a few hours. However, by applying a reverse field close to the coercive field H_c after fully magnetizing the particle, reversal can be initiated through thermal activation process within a short time scale.

In our relaxation measurements, thin film was first magnetized at 300 K in a field of 46 kOe applied perpendicular to its plane. The field was then reversed to a desired value H ($\leq H_{c\perp}$) in one step, and sample moment was monitored as a function of time over a period of 2.5 hours. Fig. 4.13 shows the decay of magnetization as a function

of time at different values of reversed fields. The presence of two distinct regimes of time in the figure indicates that there are two different activation processes leading to the relaxation of the system. A distribution in grain size is a possible reason for this behavior. The data of Fig. 4.13 have been fitted to the Néel-Brown model [178] given as $M(t) = M_0 \exp(-t/\tau)$, where M_0 is the magnetization at $t = 0$ and $M(t)$ the remanent magnetization at time t after removal of the field, τ is the relaxation time defined as $1/\tau = f_0 \exp(-E(H)/k_\beta T)$, f_0 is a frequency factor of the order of 10^9 sec^{-1} and $E(H) = K_u V(1 - H/H_k)^2$ the energy barrier in a reverse field of magnitude H . Here V , K_u and H_k denote particle volume, anisotropy energy density and anisotropy field ($=2K_u/M_s$) respectively [179]. It appears that the relaxation rate of magnetization increases rapidly as the absolute value of the magnetic field is increased. Using the above formula and approximating the grains to be spherical, we extract the activation volume whose width is $\approx 4.7 \text{ nm}$. This is far less than the diameter ($\approx 200 \text{ nm}$) of the disc-shaped magnetic particles seen in Fig. 4.12. This discrepancy points towards inadequacy of the model used.

The relaxation behavior of an assembly of single-domain particles can deviate from the ideal Néel - Brown picture due to several reasons which prominently include, multi-domain nature of particles, interaction between the particles and a distribution in their size. Our MFM images, however, do not show any well-defined sub-domains in the nanograins. Interaction amongst particles on the other hand leads to an apparent enhancement rather than a decrease in the activation volume. One could argue that the demagnetization process occurs via a curling mode in which the magnetization continuously curls around the particle center [180]. This can, in principle, lead to a smaller activation energy for demagnetization. A simple calculation for our disc-shaped grains of diameter $\approx 200 \text{ nm}$ and thickness $\approx 50 \text{ nm}$ with anisotropy axis perpendicular to the disc plane shows that reversed spins on a circular ring of width $\approx 60 \text{ nm}$ around the periphery of the disc would be sufficient

to make the net magnetization zero. The width of this rim is within the accuracy of MFM measurements.

4.3 Conclusions

CoPt films of 20 to 100 nm thickness were successfully grown using Pulsed Laser Deposition (PLD) technique. While the changes in the crystallographic structure of the films depend solely on the T_d , the microstructure and magnetization characteristics are decided by the growth rate. For the films deposited at $T_d \approx 600$ °C on (001) oriented single crystal substrates of MgO, SrTiO₃ and LaAlO₃, there are no significant differences in crystallographic ordering. X-ray diffraction and magnetization studies show a clear fcc phase with in-plane magnetization and a narrow hysteresis loop of width ≈ 200 Oe. The near-complete chemical ordering which is achieved at $T_d \geq 700$ °C, becomes predominantly c-axis oriented as the deposition temperature is raised to 800 °C. The magnetic coercivity of these films increases as the L1₀ phase fraction grows with T_d and its orientation becomes out of film plane.

Interestingly however, the epitaxial strain parameter which is related to the mismatch between the lattice parameters of fcc/L1₀ phases and that of the substrate stays neutral at the high G_r , but becomes crucial when the growth rate is reduced to ≈ 0.4 Å/sec. Low growth rate (≈ 0.4 Å/sec) reveals granularity even in 50 nm thick films. Here the structure changes from a self-similar fractal pattern to nanograins as the T_d is raised from 700 to 800 °C. Local magnetic moment associated with these systems has been probed by MFM which reveals in the 800 °C sample, clearly distinguishable nanodots with reverse magnetization. The simple model of coherent rotation of magnetization seems to be insufficient to explain the relaxation dynamics of these single-domain islands.

5. EPITAXIAL MISMATCH INDUCED GRANULARITY IN CoPt/NbN BILAYER SYSTEMS

5.1 Introduction

Hybrid superconductor-ferromagnet (SC-FM) structures have generated a considerable amount of interest in recent years as these provide model systems to understand the antagonism between superconductivity and ferromagnetism [41, 45, 47, 51, 59–62, 73, 181–191]. A rich variety of phenomena such as π -phase shift [41, 181], triplet pairing [41, 182], field-enhanced superconductivity [51, 183], domain wall superconductivity [61, 62] and enhanced flux pinning [73, 184–187] etc. have been reported in SC-FM structures. An important issue that needs to be considered while addressing the physics of SC-FM-SC and FM-SC-FM heterostructures is the difference in the crystallographic structure and the degree of strain in the top and bottom SC or FM layers, and interdiffusion at interfaces which could impart different physical properties to the top and bottom layers.

Here we report investigations of domain wall superconductivity, flux pinning and granularity issues in a strongly type-II superconductor placed in close proximity of a magnetic thin film. The system investigated consists of a bilayer of A1 phase (fcc) CoPt ferromagnet and NbN (rocksalt) superconductor grown on MgO (001). NbN and CoPt were chosen as constituents of the SC-FM bilayer since their respective

superconducting and magnetic properties can be modified in a controlled way by altering the deposition conditions [67, 163, 192]. Two different bilayer systems with reversed deposition sequence have been investigated to address superconductivity and magnetism vis-a-vis crystallographic structure and exchange field-induced proximity effects. We note that while the lattice mismatch has a minor effect on superconductivity of the bottom NbN layer in CoPt-NbN/MgO system, in the NbN-CoPt/MgO bilayer it makes the NbN film to adopt a strain-induced granular structure, which has interesting repercussions on its superconducting response.

5.2 Sample fabrication

The CoPt-NbN/MgO and NbN-CoPt/MgO bilayers with 50 nm thick CoPt and NbN layers in each case were deposited on (001) MgO at 600 °C by Pulsed Laser Ablation of Nb and CoPt targets in 99.9999 % pure nitrogen environment. The surface topography of the bilayers was analyzed using high resolution Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), which showed a smooth morphology for the CoPt-NbN/MgO system but a granular structure with typical feature size of 75 to 100 nm in NbN-CoPt/MgO bilayer. For measurements of magnetoresistance and critical current density (J_c), samples were processed using standard photolithography and Ar⁺ ion milling to produce 500 μm long and 160 μm wide bridges. After removing the photoresist, silver pads were deposited in a four-probe configuration by thermal evaporation for electrical contact.

5.3 Results and discussion

In Fig. 5.1(a) we have plotted the temperature dependence of resistance of the two bilayers, along with data for a pure NbN film for comparison. The latter shows a sharp transition ($\Delta T \approx 0.5$ K) with the onset of superconductivity at 15.5 K. The CoPt-NbN/MgO bilayer also displays a sharp transition of width ≈ 0.5 K with T_c

Fig. 5.1: Panel (a) shows the temperature dependence of resistance for pure NbN, NbN-CoPt/MgO and CoPt-NbN/MgO bilayer systems. χ' and χ'' for all the three systems as a function of temperature have been plotted in panel (b).

onset at 15.3 K. The other bilayer (NbN-CoPt/MgO), however, has a substantially reduced T_c (≈ 13.7 K) and a sizeable broadening of the transition (≈ 1.4 K).

Fig. 5.1(b) shows the real and imaginary components of the fundamental susceptibility of the same samples. The frequency, and amplitude of the ac field applied perpendicular to the plane of the film, in these experiments are 121 Hz and 1 Oe, respectively. The real part $\chi'(T)$ of the complex susceptibility $\chi(T) = \chi'(T) + i\chi''(T)$ reflects the strength of the induced shielding currents, while the imaginary part $\chi''(T)$ is connected to energy dissipation in the material. The drop of $\chi'(T)$, whose onset corresponds to the temperature where the resistance (R) goes to zero is

reasonably sharp for both pure NbN film as well as for the CoPt-NbN/MgO bilayer, indicating a homogeneous superconductor. However, for the bilayer where the NbN is deposited on top of CoPt, both χ' and χ'' show significant broadening. For inhomogeneous superconductor with distinctly different intergrain and intragrain critical currents, the χ'' peak generally splits into two components, each corresponding to peak dissipation in superconducting grains and in intergranular material [193]. The fact that we do not see two distinct peaks in the χ'' data for NbN-CoPt/MgO system suggests insignificant suppression of the order parameter in the intergrain material of the NbN layer. However, the overall suppression of T_c seen here compared to the T_c of the bilayer where NbN is deposited first, seems to indicate a perturbation of the electronic structure by stress or chemical doping which lowers the critical temperature. In order to address these issues, we have undertaken X-ray diffraction studies of the bilayer films.

Fig. 5.2 (Panel 'a' and 'b' respectively) shows the diffraction profiles of NbN-CoPt/MgO and CoPt-NbN/MgO along with the profiles of single layer CoPt (panel 'c'), NbN (panel 'd') and bare MgO substrate (panel 'e'). The single layer CoPt film shows only one peak at $2\theta = 48.13^\circ$ which corresponds to the (200) reflection of the disordered A1 (fcc) phase. Single layer NbN also shows the characteristic (200) and (400) reflections of the fcc phase indicating a highly textured growth along [001] direction of MgO. While all these characteristic reflections of the [001] growth are seen in CoPt-NbN/MgO bilayer (panel 'b') as well, the NbN peaks are not discernible in the reverse bilayer geometry (panel 'a'), where NbN was grown on CoPt, suggesting a granular structure of the nitride. These results reveal that film growth dynamics is greatly controlled by the amount of interfacial strain induced by the cubic (100) MgO whose lattice parameter 'a' is 4.21 Å. NbN is also cubic with $a = 4.39$ Å. The magnetic alloy CoPt, when grown on (100) MgO at ≤ 600 °C has a disordered fcc structure with a lattice parameter of 3.772 Å [194]. The

Fig. 5.2: X-ray diffraction profiles of (a) NbN-CoPt/MgO, (b) CoPt-NbN/MgO, (c) CoPt, (d) NbN thin films deposited at 600 °C on single crystal (001) cut MgO. The diffraction profile of single crystal MgO (001) is also shown at the bottom panel. In panel (c) and (d) peaks of A1 phase CoPt and rocksalt NbN respectively are identified with miller indices.

lattice mismatch for epitaxial growth of layer ‘A’ on layer ‘B’ can be characterized in terms of the strain parameter ϵ defined as $\epsilon = \frac{d_A - d_B}{d_A} \times 100$ where d_A and d_B are the lattice parameters of ‘A’ and ‘B’ respectively. This gives ϵ of $\approx 4.1\%$, $\approx -11.6\%$, $\approx -16.4\%$ and $\approx 14.1\%$ for NbN-MgO, CoPt-MgO, CoPt-NbN and NbN-CoPt systems respectively. In Fig. 5.3 we sketch the stacking of the unstrained unit cells in NbN, CoPt and MgO starting with MgO at the bottom. Dotted lines in the figure represents ideal coherent epitaxy in conformity with the substrate. The origin of in-plane tensile strain on CoPt and compressive strain on NbN under coherent epitaxy can be visualized from this figure.

It is interesting to note that in spite of a large strain parameter ($\epsilon \approx -16.4\%$), CoPt prefers to grow epitaxially with a slight change ($\approx 0.2\%$) in lattice parameter

Fig. 5.3: Schematic illustration of strained NbN-CoPt/MgO heterostructure. Dotted lines in the figure represents ideal coherent epitaxy. Lattice mismatch is exaggerated for clarity.

from bulk when deposited on NbN [Fig. 5.2(b)]. The peak shift [$\Delta\theta \approx 0.1^\circ$] of the (200) reflection of CoPt grown on NbN/MgO can be attributed to an improper growth due to mismatch. On the other hand, the large compressive strain ($\sim 14.1\%$) experienced by NbN, when deposited on CoPt as compared to only $\approx 4.1\%$ when grown directly on MgO, forces a highly disordered growth of NbN. We believe that the rough surface texture of CoPt films on MgO as seen in our Scanning Electron Microscopy studies and originating presumably from strain ($\epsilon \approx -11.6\%$) also makes the subsequent growth of NbN disordered.

In Fig. 5.4 (a & b) we have shown isothermal magnetization at 20 K as a function of in-plane magnetic field for the bilayers, along with the data for resistance. We note that at 20 K the coercive field (H_c) of the CoPt-NbN/MgO system is ≈ 250 Oe, which is lower than the H_c of the NbN-CoPt/MgO bilayer (≈ 500 Oe) as seen in the

Fig. 5.4: Panel (a) shows isothermal magnetization and resistance as a function of magnetic field applied in-plane for CoPt-NbN/MgO system measured at 20 K. Panel (b) shows the dependence of magnetization and resistance on in-plane magnetic field for NbN-CoPt/MgO system measured at 20 K. Arrows in the figure mark the behavior of resistance on increasing and decreasing field sweeps.

M-H loop of Fig. 5.4(b). This can be understood in the following way. During the growth of the 50 nm thick NbN using the deposition conditions mentioned before, the bottom CoPt layer gets annealed for roughly about 7 - 8 minutes, which leads to a better ordering of the structure as evidenced by the enhanced intensity of (200) reflection of the A1 phase (see Fig. 5.2 patterns 'a' and 'b'). This observation is consistent with previous studies on CoPt system which reveal that the 600 $^{\circ}$ C deposited films consist of only the fcc phase and their coercive field increases with the duration of postdeposition annealing [See Chapter 4].

The isothermal resistance of the samples in the normal state (20 K) when a dc field aligned parallel to the plane of the film and directed perpendicular to current was scanned between + 3.5 kOe and - 3.5 kOe is also shown in Fig. 5.4. Arrows in the figure mark the increasing and decreasing branches of the field. For the CoPt-NbN/MgO bilayer (Fig. 5.4(a)) upon reducing the field from 3.5 kOe, where the magnetization reaches saturation and the sample is presumably in a single domain state, the resistance decreases smoothly with field, i.e., dR/dH is positive. This behavior gives way to a sudden jump in resistance when the sample reaches a truly demagnetized state at $H = H_c$. We attribute this effect to enhanced domain wall scattering of charge carriers which presumably also leads to the observed superlinear dependence of R on the increasing $|H|$ branch till the saturation field H_s is reached. For $H > H_s$, the resistance rises in a sublinear fashion. In the other bilayer, where CoPt is at the bottom, the hysteresis in the resistivity is much more pronounced.

The M-H curves of the bilayers change dramatically on entering the superconducting state as seen in Fig. 5.5. These data were taken at 5 K with in-plane field. For the CoPt-NbN/MgO bilayer, the M-H curve is dominated by the diamagnetic response of the superconducting NbN layer, showing a hysteresis loop typical of a type-II superconductor. However, for the NbN-CoPt/MgO bilayer, the ferromagnetic component of magnetization is distinctly seen. The sudden jump in magnetization at ± 500 Oe coincides exactly with the coercive field (H_c) seen in the M-H loop taken at 20 K (Fig. 5.4(b)). Since the moment of CoPt is not expected to change below 20 K because of its large Curie temperature (≈ 710 K) [31], the true diamagnetic response of the superconductor can be extracted by subtracting the 20 K data from the 5 K data. The continuous M-H curves in Fig. 5.5 (a & b) are the true diamagnetic response. We can use the Bean critical state model [193] to extract the screening critical current density J_c from these M-H data. At field $H \approx 550$ Oe which is larger than the coercive field of both type of bilayers, the J_c

Fig. 5.5: Panel (a) and (b) show the in-plane magnetization as a function of applied magnetic field measured at 5 K for CoPt-NbN/MgO and NbN-CoPt/MgO system respectively. Contribution of superconducting NbN to total magnetization is extracted by subtracting 5 K data from 20 K data and is shown in the figures as continuous line.

of CoPt-NbN/MgO system is larger by a factor of $\simeq 3.5$ compared to the J_c of the NbN-CoPt/MgO heterostructure. The large suppression of J_c in the latter structure suggests a granular character of its NbN layer. It is worth pointing out that the actual flux density in these films of thickness (≈ 50 nm) smaller than the London penetration depth ($\approx 200 - 250$ nm) will be lower due to the dipolar field of the CoPt layer which induces reverse flux. However, the presence of the ferromagnetic layer will not affect the relative magnitude of J_c in the two cases as long as the field is greater than the coercive field.

Now we discuss how the superconductivity in a granular and a homogeneous film

Fig. 5.6: (a) Plot of critical current density J_c calculated from current-voltage characteristics using a field criterion of $10 \mu\text{V}/\text{cm}$ of NbN, CoPt-NbN/MgO and NbN-CoPt/MgO as a function of reduced temperature. Open symbols and solid symbols represent the data for zero-field and 300 Oe perpendicular field ($\vec{H} \parallel \hat{n}$) measurements respectively, where \hat{n} is unit vector normal to the plane of the film. (b) Temperature dependence of J_c with in-plane magnetic field for both the bilayers. In the inset letters A and B mark the points on a typical M-H loop at which the measurements of J_c were carried out. While open symbols in panel (b) represent data taken at point A, J_c values for fully demagnetized state (point B) are plotted as solid symbols.

is affected when it is placed in proximity of a ferromagnet through measurement of transport critical current density and its temperature and angular dependence. Fig. 5.6(a) presents the J_c measured with a voltage criterion of $10 \mu\text{V}/\text{cm}$ as a function of reduced temperature (T/T_c) for both the bilayers and a single layer NbN film.

Here T_c denotes the temperature corresponding to the zero resistance state of the samples. For the bilayer sample CoPt-NbN/MgO, the J_c at $T/T_c \geq 0.9$ is same ($\approx 6.0 \times 10^5$ A/cm²) as that of a single layer NbN film. For the other bilayer film (NbN-CoPt/MgO) however, the J_c is highly suppressed. For example, at $T/T_c = 0.8$ it is only $\approx 1.5 \times 10^5$ A/cm². Fig. 5.6 also shows the J_c vs. T/T_c plots of the two bilayers when a 300 Oe field is applied perpendicular to the plane of the film. We note that the field-induced suppression of J_c is marginally higher in the case of NbN-CoPt/MgO heterostructure. The temperature dependence of J_c is generally expressed by a phenomenological expression of the type,

$$J_c(T) = J_c(0)(1 - T/T_c)^\beta, \quad (5.1)$$

where $J_c(0)$ and β are used as fitting parameters. In the Ginzburg-Landau (GL) mean-field description of J_c , the prefactor $J_c(0)$ is a measure of the depairing current and the exponent β is $3/2$ [195]. For a highly granular system where superconducting grains are separated by insulating material, the Ambegaokar-Baratoff model can be used to describe the $J_c(T)$ data [195]. Here $J_c(0)$ is related to superconducting gap parameter and the exponent $\beta \approx 1$ at low temperatures. The data shown in Fig. 5.6 have been fitted to Eq. 5.1. The $J_c(0)$ and β for the NbN/MgO, CoPt-NbN/MgO and NbN-CoPt/MgO in zero field are ($\approx 7.81 \times 10^6$ A/cm², 0.93), ($\approx 1.65 \times 10^7$ A/cm², 1.19) and ($\approx 1.64 \times 10^6$ A/cm², 1.40) respectively. For the first two samples, since the fitting has been done over a very limited range of T/T_c , too much significance can not be given to $J_c(0)$ and β . However, for NbN-CoPt/MgO excellent fitting is seen for T/T_c ranging from 0.5 to ≈ 1 . It is interesting to note that while the NbN in this sample has a substantially reduced J_c , the β remains close to the GL value. The large value of β here suggests a robust coupling between NbN grains [195].

In order to examine how the state of magnetization of the CoPt film affects superconductivity in NbN, we have measured the temperature dependence of J_c with in-plane field [Fig. 5.6(b)] corresponding to points A and B of the hysteresis loop as shown in the inset of Fig. 5.6(b). Since at point A of the loop the sample is fully saturated, it should behave like a single domain magnetic entity. Point B of the loop corresponds to a fully demagnetized state where the sample consists of randomly oriented domains. The direction of magnetization from one domain to the next can change either by out-of-plane rotation of spins, which constitutes a Bloch wall or by in-plane rotation as in the case of a Néel wall [3]. Obviously, a Bloch wall will lead to magnetic flux into the NbN layer whereas for a Néel wall the flux remains confined in the ferromagnetic film. A Bloch wall is therefore expected to reduce the J_c of the film. The J_c of the NbN-CoPt/MgO and CoPt-NbN/MgO films measured at positions A and B of the hysteresis loop is shown in Fig. 5.6(b). No discernible difference in the critical current in the two cases is seen suggesting that in these 50 nm CoPt films the domain walls are of Néel type.

In order to address further the likely perturbation of superconductivity in NbN by magnetic domain structure of CoPt layer, we show in Fig. 5.7 the angular dependence of flux flow resistivity at three points of the hysteresis loop measured at a temperature where resistance drops by $\approx 95\%$ of its normal state value in zero-field. The orientation of current \vec{I} , magnetization \vec{M} and magnetic field \vec{H} vectors is shown in the inset of the figure. The angle ϕ is between \vec{H} and film normal \hat{n} . At saturation points A and D of the loop the \vec{M} vector is always perpendicular to \vec{J} , either along $+\hat{y}$ or $-\hat{y}$. The flux flow resistivity of both bilayers at $H = \pm 1500$ Oe (points A and D of hysteresis) is characterized by two sharp cusps at $\phi = \pm 90^\circ$ and maximum dissipation at $\phi = 0^\circ$, i.e., when the field is normal to the film surface. If we attribute the flux flow resistivity only to the normal component of the field ($H\cos\phi$), then ρ_f must go linearly in $H\cos\phi$ following the relation for flux

Fig. 5.7: The resistance of both CoPt-NbN/MgO (right Y-axis) and NbN-CoPt/MgO (left Y-axis) systems in the flux flow regime as a function of the angle ϕ between the applied magnetic field and film normal (\hat{n}) at a temperature in the transition region, where the sample resistance is 5% of the zero-field normal state resistance. Magnetic field direction was changed in a step of 2 degree while it remained always orthogonal to the current direction ($\vec{H} \perp \vec{J}$). Zeroes on the X-axis correspond to field angle normal to the film surface. A constant bias current of $1 \mu\text{A}$ was used for all the measurements. Right inset shows schematically the direction of current flow (\vec{J}), magnetization vector (\vec{M}) and the direction of magnetic field (\vec{H}) which makes angle ϕ with \hat{n} . The letters A, B, C and D in the middle panel mark the points on a typical M-H loop at which R was measured. Left inset shows the dependence of resistance extracted from the data presented in the main panel (curves A and D) as a function of normal component of the applied field for both the samples.

flow resistance $\rho_f/\rho_N \approx H/H_{c2}$, where ρ_N is the normal state resistance and H_{c2} the upper critical field [196]. In the right inset of Fig. 5.7 we show variation of ρ_f vs. $H\cos\phi$ for CoPt-NbN/MgO and NbN-CoPt/MgO bilayers. In the former case, where superconductivity is robust in NbN, the flux-flow resistance shows a linear dependence on $H\cos\phi$. For the sample where NbN is on the top, however, the scaling of ρ_f with $H\cos\phi$ is poor, indicating that this film can not be treated as an infinite superconducting plane. In Fig. 5.7 we have also plotted the angular dependence of R_f at points B and C of the hysteresis loop. The large dissipation seen at the

coercive field in NbN-CoPt/MgO over a range of angles around $\phi = 0$ again points towards the granular nature of the NbN.

5.4 Conclusions

We have studied the crystallographic structure, magnetic ordering and superconducting properties of ferromagnet-superconductor bilayers made of CoPt and NbN grown on single crystal MgO in two different geometries, with either NbN or CoPt in contact with the substrate. By comparing the SC response of these bilayers with that of an NbN film, we conclude that the ferromagnetism of CoPt has no discernible effect on the bulk SC properties of the NbN. This also leads us to believe that the magnetic domain walls in CoPt in both bilayers are of the Néel type. While the ferromagnetism of CoPt has no deleterious effects, the polycrystalline nature of NbN deposited on CoPt imparts it a granular character which reflects itself in a reduced T_c , in the temperature dependence of J_c , and in the variation of flux-flow resistance as a function of the angle between applied field and film normal.

6. INHOMOGENEOUS VORTEX STATE AND FIELD-ENHANCED SUPERCONDUCTIVITY

6.1 Introduction

The pinning of magnetic flux lines in a superconducting (SC) film by random and ordered arrays of ferromagnetic (FM) dots and multidomain magnetic films has been a topic of considerable interest [45, 46, 48, 51, 52, 60–62, 72, 73, 185]. Such ferromagnet-superconductor heterostructures of conventional low T_c materials and high T_c cuprates with in-plane as well as perpendicular magnetic anisotropy have been investigated, and the effects of commensuration between periodicity of the dot arrays and of the flux line lattice in field dependence of critical current density (J_c) has been seen [46]. An important consequence of the inhomogeneous magnetic field produced by the array of dots and granular magnetic films is the formation of a local field-free state when the FM-SC hybrid is placed in an external magnetic field. This effect has been variously called field-enhanced superconductivity [51, 60], magnetization controlled superconductivity [72] and domain wall superconductivity [61, 62]. The phenomenon is relatively easy to comprehend in the case of periodic magnetic dots with perpendicular anisotropy. The effective field normal (\hat{z}) to the plane (xy-plane) of the film placed in an external field $\vec{H} = H_0\hat{z}$ is a function of the xy coordinates. It derives positive contribution from the magnetic induction

$B\hat{z}$ of the dot at points underneath the dots, and in between the dots the dipolar contribution is negative. Under idealized conditions, magnetic-field-free regions in the film can exist for a non-zero external field $H > H_{c1}$. The situation in the case of magnetic dots with in-plane anisotropy is not this straightforward. The in-plane magnetic dipole produces a vortex and an antivortex in the superconducting film at the opposite ends of the dipole [48]. For an ordered array of magnetic dipoles, a vortex-antivortex pair would exist between the two successive dipoles along their length if the interdipole interaction is negligible.

Here we show that in FM-SC systems where the FM domains/islands produce spatial inhomogeneities of the SC order parameter, the observed FIS can derive significant contribution from different mobilities of the magnetic flux identified by two distinct critical states in the inhomogeneous superconductor. Our experiments on nanoengineered bilayer of ferromagnetic CoPt and superconducting NbN where CoPt/NbN islands separated by a granular NbN, lend support for this alternative explanation of FIS in certain class of FM-SC hybrids.

6.2 Sample fabrication

Thin film bilayers of CoPt and NbN each 50 nm thick, were deposited on (001) MgO substrate at 600 °C using Pulsed Laser Ablation of CoPt and Nb targets respectively. The bilayer film was first patterned with standard lithography and Ar^+ ion milling into a $100\ \mu\text{m} \times 500\ \mu\text{m}$ bridge as shown in Fig. 6.1. The top CoPt layer was then structured in simple square patterns using a Ga^{3+} Focused Ion Beam (FIB) milling facility (Dual-beam Nova 600 NanoLab, FEI Company). The shape and size of the squares were examined using the Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) of the FIB system. Fig. 6.1(b) shows a typical Scanning Electron Micrograph of the patterned bilayer. The size of each CoPt element in the pattern is $0.5 \times 0.5\ \mu\text{m}^2$ with 50 nm spacing in between. The active area of the sample on which transport measurements

Fig. 6.1: (a) The basic form of sample design. Dimensions of the micro-bridge and planer array of CoPt islands have been exaggerated out of proportion for better visualization while actual values are mentioned in the text. In order to achieve a sufficiently small beam diameter and to maintain a slow etching rate, the experiments were carried out with the ion acceleration voltage and current set to 20 kV and 4 pA, respectively. Panel (b) shows a typical Scanning Electron Micrograph of the patterned bilayer and (c) AFM and (d) MFM images of the patterned sample. AFM and MFM measurements were performed simultaneously on thermally demagnetized samples at lift height of 40 nm.

were carried out contains 10×210 square elements.

6.3 Results and discussion

Since the central result of this chapter is a consequence of inhomogeneities in the superconducting and ferromagnetic order parameters, we first establish these inhomogeneities in the patterned samples. Fig. 6.2 presents the resistance of both patterned as well as unpatterned samples in a narrow temperature range around superconducting transition. While the unpatterned film shows a clear and reason-

Fig. 6.2: Temperature dependence of resistance of the patterned and unpatterned bilayers. A clear two-step superconducting transition is seen in the patterned film. Inset shows critical current density. While the solid and open circles represent data for zero-field and 300 Oe perpendicular field ($\vec{H} \parallel \hat{n}$) measurements respectively for unpatterned film, solid and open triangles respectively are the data of patterned film measured at 0 and 300 Oe perpendicular field ($\vec{H} \parallel \hat{n}$). Solid lines through data points are fits to the relation $J_c(T) = J_c(0)(1 - T/T_c)^\beta$. Values of the exponent β extracted from the fits are listed in the figure.

ably sharp transition ($\Delta T \approx 0.5$ K) with T_c onset at ≈ 15.3 K, the resistance of the patterned film exhibits a two step structure corresponding to the superconducting transition of the two components. As seen in Fig. 6.2, the first drop in resistance occurs at ≈ 15.1 K in which the resistance decreases by ≈ 60 % of its normal state value. The second transition starts at ≈ 13 K culminating in zero resistance at ≈ 11.8 K. The observed change from the single-step to two-step transition on nanostructuring is presumably a result of Ga ion damage. This feature, however, provides the unique advantage of addressing magnetic-field-induced superconductivity in a granular medium.

Inset of Fig. 6.2 compares the temperature dependence of J_c of the nanostruc-

tured and a plane bilayer film. The J_c (T) data of pristine bilayer shown in Fig 5.6(a) is replotted here for comparison. These data were collected in zero-field and in 300 Oe field applied perpendicular to the plane of the sample. The zero-field J_c of the unpatterned film quickly reaches the limit of measurement ($\approx 1.25 \times 10^6$ A/cm²) which is set by the width of the bridge (≈ 160 μ m) and maximum dc current (≈ 100 mA). However, a pronounced reduction in the critical current density of the patterned film is seen, as compared to the J_c of the pristine bilayer. Since the capacity of the structure to carry dissipation-less current is determined by their low T_c links, a suppressed growth of J_c on lowering the temperature suggests that the channels of NbN connecting CoPt/NbN islands are granular. To address this issue further, we fit the J_c (T) data to Eq. 5.1. The fitted curves are shown as solid lines along with the values of β extracted from the fits. For the patterned film in zero-field $\beta = 1.27$ and $J_c(0) \approx 9.8 \times 10^6$ A/cm². A pronounced suppression of the J_c is seen at 300 Oe perpendicular field. The exponent β and $J_c(0)$ are now ≈ 1.63 and $\approx 4.2 \times 10^6$ A/cm² respectively. A similar trend is seen in the pristine bilayer although the range of temperature over which fitting has been done is limited. For a granular system one expects the Ambegaokar-Baratoff (AB) type temperature dependence of J_c at low temperatures with $\beta \approx 1$ and $J_c(0)$ being proportional to the ratio of the zero-temperature gap parameter and normal state resistance of the junction. Although a granular character of the sample is evident from the two steps seen in Fig. 6.1, a transition from the AB to GL dependence of J_c (T) is seen when the Josephson coupling energy between the grains is not negligible compared to the superconducting condensation energy of the grain [195].

While it was not possible to measure the magnetic state of the patterned film with SQUID magnetometry, we have used room temperature MFM to visualize domain structure of the CoPt islands. Fig. 6.1(c) and (d) show the AFM and MFM micrographs respectively, taken from the same spot on the film. The AFM

Fig. 6.3: *Top panel shows resistance vs. field (R - H) of an unpatterned bilayer at 20 K. Arrows in the figure mark the direction of field change. The R vs. H plot of the patterned film in the normal state (20 K) is shown in the bottom panel.*

image of the sample is quite similar to its SEM image (Fig. 6.1(b)). The bright and dark features in MFM represent domains of reversed magnetization. Since each patterned CoPt island has two such domains, it is clear that they are in a thermally demagnetized state. The continuation of the bright and dark contrast from one island to other also suggests that there exist some magnetic coupling between the physically separated islands.

Fig. 6.3 shows the isothermal resistance of the sample at 20 K. The R - H data of Fig 5.4(a) for unpatterned film is reproduced here in a field window of + 2 to - 2 kOe. The R (H) curve is symmetric on field reversal for both unpatterned and patterned films. It should be noted that the current in these bilayers flows through NbN and CoPt films in a parallel configuration. Although NbN has negligible magnetoresistance, the parallel configuration make a quantitative analysis of the R (H) data difficult. In the lower panel of Fig. 6.3 we show the R (H) curve of the pat-

Fig. 6.4: Magnetic field dependence of the flux flow resistance of the nanoengineered CoPt-NbN/MgO bilayer is shown in panel (a) to (g) at several values of the reduced temperature T/T_c . Small arrows in panel (e) mark the direction of field sweep. The critical field H^* at which dissipation appears on ramping the field from zero value has also been marked in the figures with vertical arrows. The current used in these measurements was kept fixed at 2.95 mA, which corresponds to I_c at ≈ 9.8 K. Panel (h) shows the field dependence of resistance of the unpatterned sample measured at $T/T_c = 0.89$.

terned film. Here the resistance has a significantly suppressed field dependence in the fully saturated state. Also, unlike the case of the continuous bilayer, here the drop in resistance is much larger on reaching $-H_c$ from the positive field side. This low resistance state persists for field $|H| > H_c$ and $< H_s$. When the $|H|$ exceeds H_s , the high field limit of resistance is approached first rapidly and then gradually. This strikingly different behavior of $R(H)$ as compared to that of unpatterned bilayer seen here is consequence of magnetic granularity introduced by nanoscale patterning.

In Fig. 6.4, we present a set of R vs. H measurements on the nanostructured

film at several values of the reduced temperature T/T_c , where T_c is the temperature (≈ 11.8 K) at which the zero-resistance state is reached. The magnetic field in these measurements, applied in the plane of the film and orthogonal to current was scanned in units of kOe following the cycle $0 \rightarrow 3.5 \rightarrow 0 \rightarrow -3.5 \rightarrow 0$. The increasing and decreasing field branches of the R vs. H curves have been marked by arrows [see panel 'e']. A constant current density of 1×10^6 A/cm², which corresponds to the J_c at 9.8 K ($T/T_c = 0.83$) was used for resistance measurements. At the low reduced temperature ($T/T_c = 0.79$), the resistance first remains zero with increasing field. This is expected as the excitation current density J is smaller than the J_c at this reduced temperature. However, as the field increases, J_c continues to drop and at $H = H^*$ (marked in the figure), the J becomes larger than J_c and the sample goes in a dissipative state. Here the dependence of R is linear on H , as expected in the flux-flow regime of the mixed state. On reversing the field, however, the resistance drops to zero much faster. The dissipation-less state appears at higher field $H (> H^*)$ in the reverse branch of the loop. A similar hysteretic behavior is seen at the higher values of the reduced temperature. In Fig. 6.4 (h) we show the results of a similar measurement performed on an unpatterned bilayer. In this case the R vs. H curve is completely reversible. It is clear from these measurements that the hysteretic behavior of R vs. H curves is a consequence of the nanopatterning. This is the central result of our work. A key question to ask here is how the R - H curves behave when the external field is made collinear with the current. We find that the R - H curves are similar within the accuracy of these measurements for the Lorentz-force-free configuration ($\vec{J} \parallel \vec{H}$).

In Fig. 6.5(a) and (b) we summarize the observations of a field-assisted reentrant superconducting state in terms of a field-temperature (H - T) phase diagram. Fig. 6.5(c) shows a sketch of the R - H curve where critical points have been marked by letters A, B, C, D, E and F. Point A corresponds to the critical field where supercon-

Fig. 6.5: The dark areas in panel (a) and (b) show the H - T phase space where the field-assisted superconductivity exists as shown by results of Fig. 6.4. Panel (c) shows a sketch of the R - H curve in which critical points (see the text) have been marked by letters A, B, C, D, E and F. The contours of the points C and D as a function of temperature are shown in (a) while scanning the field from $+H_{max}$ to $-H_{max}$. Contours of points F and A with temperature are shown in panel (b) for the field scan in reverse direction from $-H_{max}$ to $+H_{max}$. The coercive field $H_c = \pm 250$ Oe is drawn by a pair of horizontal lines in both the phase diagrams.

ductivity disappears on ramping up the field, point B denotes the maximum applied field and point C is where superconductivity reappears on reducing the field from its maximum value. Similarly, points D and F mark destruction and reappearance of superconductivity on the reverse branch of the loop while E corresponds to the maximum -ve field. The contours of the points C and D as a function of temperature

Fig. 6.6: Panel (a) represents the top view of the flux distribution in the patterned bilayer when external magnetic field is applied along the film plane and orthogonal to the current direction. In-plane field lines are shown as dotted lines whereas the dipolar field penetrating the NbN channel is represented by circles and crosses. Large arrows in the middle of squares mark the direction of magnetization of CoPt islands. A side view of the dipolar field produced by the CoPt squares is sketched in panel (b). Panel (c) shows the flux distribution when field and current are collinear (Lorentz-force-free configuration). Panel (d) shows R vs. H plot in $\vec{H} \parallel \vec{J}$ configuration at $T/T_c = 0.85$.

are shown in Fig. 6.5(a), and the shaded area enclosed by them is the range of field where global superconductivity exists while scanning it from $+H_{max}$ to $-H_{max}$. Fig. 6.5(b) is the phase space of superconductivity for $-H_{max}$ to $+H_{max}$ excursion.

A viable model for correct understanding of the phase diagram of Fig. 6.5 must take into account two important features of the nanostructured sample; first, it has a periodic granularity. The CoPt-NbN squares become superconducting at ≈ 15 K, but a long-range phase coherence develops only when the CoPt-free grid becomes superconducting at ≈ 11.8 K. The patterned film therefore is characterized by two

distinct critical current densities, a large J_{cg} inside the NbN-CoPt squares and a much weaker J_{cj} in the channels separating these squares. Secondly, the CoPt islands have in-plane magnetization with coercive field ≈ 250 Oe (see Fig. 5.4) which has been marked by a pair of horizontal lines in the phase diagram of Fig. 6.5. It is clear that in most of the phase space, the CoPt islands are saturated with their magnetization parallel to $H_{external}$. A qualitative understanding of the flux distribution in the presence of a magnetic field in-plane with current can be made from Fig. 6.6(a) and (c) drawn for $\vec{H} \perp \hat{n} \perp \vec{J}$ and $\vec{H} \perp \hat{n} \parallel \vec{J}$ configurations. We first note that the dipolar field of the CoPt square produces flux lines of opposite polarity in the NbN located at the two ends of the dipole. These are marked by open circles and crosses in the top view of the square array. The flux due to external magnetic field has a different distribution in the channels and the CoPt covered NbN squares because of their different J_c 's. It can be understood in the framework of the two-level critical state model of Ji, Rzchowski, Anand, and Tinkham for flux penetration in Nb-Cu-Nb proximity junction arrays [198]. Using this model we can define two types of fluxons; (i) those pinned by pinning centers in the square (ϕ_p), and (ii), the fluxons that are confined to the channels and are free to move due to weak pinning (ϕ_f). As the external field is increased, fluxons enter the channels first supersaturating them and leading to the increase of dissipation along A-B branch of the curve in Fig. 6.5(c). The flux eventually enters the squares where it is pinned. On decreasing the field, the free flux (ϕ_f) leaks out from the channels to such an extent that the zero resistance state is reestablished along the low resistance paths marked in Fig. 6.6 at a net higher value of the external field. This is possible because there is a large pinned flux (ϕ_p) in the NbN squares.

We expect that in the $\vec{H} \perp \vec{J}$ configuration (Fig. 6.6(a)), the current flow along the channels (paths which do not cross CoPt-NbN squares) remain dissipative due to the dipolar field of CoPt. This is where the magnetization of CoPt plays an

explicit role. A similar scenario also explains reentrant superconductivity seen for the Lorentz-force-free configuration $\vec{H} \parallel \vec{J}$ sketched at the left bottom panel (c) of Fig. 6.6. A typical set of R vs. H data taken at $T/T_c = 0.85$ in $\vec{H} \parallel \vec{J}$ configuration is shown in panel (d) of Fig. 6.6. The granular NbN channels although form a continuous path for the flow of current for $\vec{H} \parallel \vec{J}$, the cores of vortices, which are already large due to a small order parameter in the channels, start overlapping, and even at low fields, the channels become resistive. The onset of resistance here has nothing to do with vortex motion under Lorentz force. This type of force-free dissipation has been seen in granular films of NbN [199].

6.4 Conclusions

The observations made in the present study have important repercussions on the phenomenon of field assisted superconductivity seen in FM-SC bilayers [60], trilayers [183] and dot structures [51]. While in the case of FM-SC-FM trilayer structures placed in an in-plane field, no inhomogeneity of the order parameter is introduced as long as each FM layer behaves like a single domain film, the same is unavoidable in bilayers at field $H < H_c$ and in dot arrays even beyond saturation. We believe that in such systems the repercussions of the two-level critical state model warrant consideration.

7. CONCLUSIONS AND SCOPE FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

A summary of the important results of this thesis is presented in this concluding chapter. Synthesis of equiatomic cobalt-platinum alloy in colloidal and thin film forms and modulation of the superconducting order parameter in mutually accommodating heterostructures of CoPt/NbN have been the focus of the thesis. Following a brief summary of the results, we conclude this chapter by identifying a few potential frontiers of further research on magnetic colloids, thin films, and ferromagnet-superconductor heterostructures.

7.1 Magnetic relaxation and superparamagnetism: CoPt nanoparticles

Cobalt platinum nanoparticles dispersed in surfactant polymer matrix were synthesized successfully using a simple and versatile technique based on Pulsed Laser Ablation of a composite alloy target in an aqueous medium. The technique is particularly suitable for preparation of binary and multi elemental alloy nanoparticles, whose size can be controlled to some extent by a judicious choice of laser ablation parameters such as laser fluence, pulse repetition rate and laser wavelength. A choice of liquid medium may also allow in-situ coating of the nanoparticles to form a core shell structure. For CoPt nanoparticles prepared using this technique the zero-field-cooled and field-cooled magnetization measurements at low-fields reveal two distinct temperatures (260 K and 4 K) where the ZFC and FC curves bifurcate from each other, corresponding to the characteristic blocking of an aggregate of superparamagnetic particles. Magnetization vs. field measurements at different temperatures show strong evidence of superparamagnetic nature of the particles. For temperatures below 4 K, the magnetization curves are hysteretic. The low coercive field (~ 400 Oe) of this assembly at 2K is essentially a characteristic of low temperature fcc phase of $\text{Co}_{0.5}\text{Pt}_{0.5}$ nanoparticles. The magnetization dynamics of these particles is examined in the framework of superparamagnetic blocking phenomenon based on log-normal size distribution. A two-particle distribution model which peak at 1.3 nm and 5.9 nm agrees with the behavior of isothermal magnetization and magnetic relaxation data. Our analysis reveals the magnetic anisotropy energy of these particles is 0.9×10^6 J/m³ and 0.1×10^6 J/m³ respectively.

7.2 CoPt films: Influence of deposition parameters

CoPt films of 20 to 100 nm thickness were successfully grown using the Pulsed Laser Deposition (PLD) technique by ablating a Co₅₀Pt₅₀ alloy target. The deposition conditions which facilitate growth of the L1₀ ordered phase of high magnetocrystalline anisotropy are clearly identified. Correlations between film morphology, crystallographic structure and magnetic properties such as magnetocrystalline anisotropy, shape and size of the hysteresis loops, coercive field and magnetic domain structure etc. have been established. We note that the crystallographic ordering in films deposited at 600 °C on single crystal substrates which offer different degree of strain is similar. These films have a disordered fcc structure with in-plane magnetization and a narrow hysteresis loop of width ≈ 200 Oe. The near-complete chemical ordering achieved at $T_d \geq 700$ °C, becomes predominantly c-axis oriented as the deposition temperature is raised to 800 °C. While the changes in the crystallographic structure of the films depend solely on T_d , the microstructure and magnetization characteristics are decided by the growth rate. It is observed that irrespective of a large difference in lattice parameters of the substrates used, there is hardly any change in morphology of the films grown on different substrates, when a high growth rate (≈ 1 Å/sec) is maintained. The microstructure of these L1₀ films evolves from a well-connected maze-like structure at $t_F = 20$ nm to a smooth and continuous film at $t_F = 50$ nm. The magnetic coercivity of these films increases as the L1₀ phase fraction grows with T_d and its orientation becomes out of film plane.

While the higher growth rate seems to suppress the effects of strain due to lattice mismatch, low growth rate (≈ 0.4 Å/sec) reveals granularity in the films even at small thickness (≈ 50 nm). Here the structure changes from a self-similar fractal pattern to nanodots as the T_d is raised from 700 to 800 °C. The reason for this topographical change appears to be the imbalance between strain and interfacial

energies, which is overridden by kinetic considerations at high G_r . AFM and MFM images of the films grown at low G_r and high T_d reveal physically separated, magnetically single-domain nanoscale island. Magnetic relaxation measurements carried out to study the relaxation dynamics of these single-domain islands show negligible decay of magnetization unless a reverse field close to the coercive field ($H_c \approx 30$ kOe) is applied. The simple picture of coherent rotation of magnetization appears incompatible with the time dependence of the remanent magnetization.

7.3 Granularity aspects: CoPt/NbN bilayer systems

The effect of strain due to lattice mismatch and of ferromagnetic (FM) exchange field on superconductivity (SC) in NbN-CoPt bilayers is investigated. Two different bilayer systems with reversed deposition sequence are grown on MgO (001) single crystals. While robust superconductivity with high critical temperature ($T_c \approx 15.3$ K) is seen in CoPt-NbN/MgO heterostructure, the NbN-CoPt/MgO shows markedly suppressed SC response. X-ray diffraction studies reveal that in spite of a large strain parameter ($\epsilon \approx -16.4\%$), CoPt grows epitaxially when deposited on NbN. The large compressive strain ($\sim 14.1\%$) experienced by NbN when deposited on CoPt, on the other hand forces a highly disordered growth of NbN. Isothermal magnetization of both the bilayers at 20 K shows square hysteresis loop with low coercive field suggesting a soft ferromagnetic state in CoPt with in-plane magnetization. The M-H curves of the bilayers change dramatically on entering the superconducting state. For the CoPt-NbN/MgO bilayer, the M-H curve is dominated by the diamagnetic response of the superconducting NbN layer, showing a hysteresis loop typical of a type-II superconductor. However, for the NbN-CoPt/MgO bilayer, the ferromagnetic component of magnetization is clearly visible. Transport critical current measurements on NbN-CoPt/MgO suggest a robust coupling between NbN grains. Also, temperature dependence of J_c at fully saturated and fully demagnetized states

in both the bilayer systems suggests that in these 50 nm CoPt films the domain walls are of Néel type. In CoPt-NbN/MgO bilayer, while the flux-flow resistance shows a linear dependence on normal component of the applied field ($H\cos\phi$), the scaling of ρ_f with $H\cos\phi$ is poor in other bilayer, indicating that this film can not be treated as an infinite superconducting plane.

In summary, the reduced SC order parameter of CoPt-NbN/MgO system, which manifests itself in T_c , temperature dependence of critical current density J_c (T), and angular (ϕ) variation of flux-flow resistivity ρ_f is shown to be a signature of the structure of NbN film and not a result of the exchange field of CoPt. The large dissipation seen at the coercive field in NbN-CoPt/MgO over a range of angles around $\phi = 0$ in ρ_f (H,T, ϕ) measurements further points towards the granular nature of NbN.

7.4 Field-enhanced superconductivity

We have addressed the issue of field-induced superconductivity in nanoengineered grids of CoPt/NbN where the CoPt-free regions have been made granular, with a reduced critical temperature. The advantage of using NbN is in its large upper critical field ($H_{c2} > 250$ kOe) which prohibits a significant perturbation of superconductivity by the CoPt, and the areas of the film covered by magnetic squares retain their high critical temperature. A two-step transition in R vs. T measurements confirms the presence of two superconducting regions in the patterned sample. The resistance (R) of the nanoengineered structures has been measured with current density $J \geq J_c$ as a function of external field \vec{H} applied in two different orientations (i) $\vec{H} \perp \vec{J} \perp \hat{n}$ and (ii) $\vec{H} \parallel \vec{J} \perp \hat{n}$, where \hat{n} is a unit vector normal to the plane of the film. In both these configurations where the field is in the plane of the film but configuration (ii) offers no Lorentz force on vortices. The R vs. H loops are hysteretic with their reverse branch showing entry into the superconducting state at fields much higher

than the field at which R appears in the forward branch. We present a different approach to understand this FIS state. It is argued to be the consequence of the granular superconducting state accompanied by the inhomogeneous ferromagnetic structure. The two-level critical state model proposed by Ji et al. [198] has been employed to understand qualitatively the H-T phase diagram of the FIS state.

7.5 Scope for further research

In this thesis we have been able to explore only a few aspects of the cobalt-platinum systems in colloidal and thin film forms, and of the heterostructures consisting of ferromagnetic and superconducting films. Here we enumerate some possible extensions of the current work.

1. Our studies on CoPt colloids (Chapter 3) have revealed that with the anisotropy energy of $0.1 \times 10^6 \text{ J/m}^3$, a $\approx 16 \text{ nm}$ diameter single domain CoPt nanoparticle would have blocking temperature of $\simeq 300 \text{ K}$. The anisotropy energy and hence the blocking temperature of CoPt can be enhanced through stabilization of the ordered fct phase on annealing at high ($\geq 600 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) temperatures. Future research in this area would involve in-situ growth of a ceramic shell around CoPt nanoparticles, so that high temperature annealing can be realized without agglomeration. Also the inability to explain the magnetization data over the entire range of temperature even with the dual log-normal distribution demands more rigorous simulations that incorporate variation of anisotropy energy with particle size.
2. In Chapter 4, we have studied the evolution of microstructure in CoPt films from a self-similar fractal pattern to a disordered assembly of nanodots of about 200 nm as the growth condition is varied. One major challenge in high density recording media is the minimization of inter-grain coupling. Further re-

search on synthesis of self-assembled ordered CoPt particles with even smaller grain size and simultaneous growth of a non magnetic spacer at the grain boundaries to reduce the transition noise between the grains would certainly be important for high density recording. Also, the simple picture of coherent rotation of magnetic moment appears incompatible with the time dependence of remanent magnetization in this system. Further work, preferably with spin polarized tunneling may shed more light on the demagnetization dynamics of these CoPt nanodots.

3. Another interesting observation from our work (Chapter 5) is nature of magnetic domain walls in CoPt/NbN bilayers. No discernible difference in the critical current in these cases is seen suggesting that in these 50 nm thick CoPt films the domain walls are of Néel type. However, The presence of Bloch walls in which direction of magnetization from one domain to the next change by out-of-plane rotation of spins, obviously, cause magnetic flux to penetrate into the NbN layer, and therefore, is expected to reduce the J_c of the film. The Bloch wall energy density decreases with increasing film thickness because of decreased magnetostatic energy. Hence the evolution of domain wall in CoPt system should be investigated as a function of film thickness.
4. The possibility of π -phase coupling in SC-FM-SC structures in CoPt/NbN system has not been studied so far, although the existence of π -phase in similar structures with clean metallic superconductors has been verified experimentally.
5. Although in FM-SC-FM layered systems the zero-field behavior of critical current density has been studied extensively in terms of the pair breaking effects of ferromagnetic layer, the influence of magnetic order on field-dependence of critical current density needs to be explored. Another important observation

in FM-SC-FM structures reported recently is domain-wall-guided superconductivity. By choosing the magnetic layers of different strength, the domain structure of the top and bottom layers can be selectively controlled. So far most of the studies in FM/SC heterostructures have been carried out on elemental superconductors in conjunction with 3d transition metal ferromagnets. This work needs to be extended to other heterostructures such as CoPt/NbN.

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